

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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TURNkey

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Revised use-cases for the FWCR Platform version 2.0 (PAR Cycle 2)

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Glossary

Acronym	Description
AR	Action research
BCRP	Business continuity and resiliency plan
DMP	Disaster management plan
DSS	Decision Support System
EEW	Earthquake early-warning
FWCR	Forecasting, early warning, consequence prediction, response
OEF	Operational earthquake forecasting
PAR	Participatory action research
RAG	Red, amber, green
RRE	Rapid response to earthquakes
TB	Test bed
TRL	Technology readiness level
UC	Use case
WP	Work package

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1 Introduction

A large part of Europe is at risk from earthquakes, as shown in Figure 1. From 2006 to 2015, Europe experienced 21 earthquake-related disasters that resulted in 1.049 fatalities, more than 18 billion Euros in economic losses, and affected 284.000 people. To address this, the TURNkey research project aims to foster seismic resilience in urban areas in Europe before, during and after a damaging earthquake. The project looks at Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), also called time-dependent hazard assessment, as well as Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) and its use, both in real-time (during an event) and in near real-time, when rapidly responding to earthquake impacts (RRE). TURNkey works towards the development of a forecasting, early warning, consequence prediction and response (FWCR) platform, which effectively integrates OEF, EEW and RRE. TURNkey's goal is to close the gap between theoretical systems and their practical application in Europe. To this end, TURNkey researchers work with potential end-users to co-design an FWCR platform that could usefully inform strategic and operational decision making in the face of seismic risk and earthquake-related disasters (Figure 2).

The methodology that underpins this approach is called participatory action research (PAR). With PAR, the people or organisations who are the focus of the research (and for whom a solution/product is being developed) take an active part in the research process. They help researchers interpret and understand the situation, help shape the findings/solution and ultimately use the latter to inform their actions and decision-making. The goal of PAR in TURNkey is to understand how end-users would use the FWCR platform in practical situations to improve their earthquake resilience - and then to leverage this information to inform the design of the TURNkey system in a way that addresses the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) to its uptake and use. Given this, PAR in TURNkey involves both potential end-users of the system as well as those responsible for its design and development (i.e., the TURNkey scientists and engineers). The end-users included in PAR are civil protection, first responders, general business and critical infrastructure providers. TURNkey works with potential end-users based in its 6 geographical testbeds: Romania (TB-1); France (TB-2); Iceland (TB-3); Greece (TB-4); Italy (TB-5) and the Netherlands (TB-6).

The TURNkey concept model is being developed over three PAR cycles. This report describes the process and findings of the 2nd PAR cycle in the TURNkey project. In light of these findings, the report reviews the end-user use cases that were developed for TURNkey during the 1st PAR cycle (which have been reported in D2.6) and revises them in light of the discussions with end-users and TURNkey scientists, engineers and software developers that occurred during the 2nd PAR cycle. The report lays the foundation for the 3rd and final round of PAR that will be conducted for TURNkey. It will also inform TURNkey deliverable D7.7, which will provide end-users with an (exemplar) model Business Continuity and Resilience Plan (BCRP) and Disaster Management Plan (DMP) framework for integrating the TURNkey FWCR platform into their disaster management planning process. This report provides the following:

- Review of the key lessons from the 1st PAR Cycle
- Online workshops with potential end-users using a virtual demonstrator (process and findings)
- SWOT analysis with TURNkey scientists and engineers (process and findings)
- TURNkey application workshop around a hypothetical hospital scenario (process and findings)
- Consortium-wide reflection on findings from the 2nd PAR Cycle (process and findings)
- Revised end-user use cases
- Revised table of TURNkey features, what end-users want vs what is possible and in scope
- A revised version of the FWCR concept model
- A conclusion and next steps

This report is intended as an internal working report for use by members of the TURNkey project in the development of the TURNkey FWCR platform. The report should be considered as a work in progress which will be amended and modified throughout the TURNkey project to reflect emerging issues identified through the 3rd PAR cycle.

Figure 1 European Seismic Hazard Map, European Commission (2013)

2 Participatory Action Research

As outlined, the TURNkey project is using PAR principles to guide the design, development and testing of the TURNkey FWCR platform. PAR is sometimes used in software and product development to develop strategic level use cases (e.g., Brandt, 2004). This approach allows for end-user needs to inform design specifications (operational, socioeconomic, etc.) and to guide the development and testing of models and tools. Use cases are used to capture the user (actor) point of view while describing the functional requirements of the system. TURNkey uses this approach to integrate outputs from TURNkey's technical work packages (WPs) (i.e., WP3, WP4, WP5-in part) with outputs from TURNkey's socio-economic WPs (i.e., WP1, WP2, WP5, WP7). PAR based use cases are developed on the basis of three iterative cycles of planning, implementation, reflection and review (Smith, 1996; 2001, 2007, 2017). This process is depicted below in Figure 3. The use cases developed and fine-tuned during the three PAR cycles guide the development of the TURNkey FWCR platform in WP6. The outputs from the three PAR cycles take the format of narrative stories that describe the research journey used to develop and test the use-cases along with any revisions needed to the use-cases identified during their evaluation. The 1st PAR Cycle was reported in D2.6, whereas this report describes the process and findings of the 2nd PAR Cycle. D7.7 will report the results from the 3rd PAR Cycle.

Figure 2 TURNkey multidisciplinary methodology (source: TURNkey Grant Agreement)

The original timescale envisaged feedback from the PAR cycles to WP6 at months 18, 24 and 32. However, due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the fieldwork associated with PAR, these timescales have been adjusted to reflect the practical issues associated with data collection from the Testbeds (TB) and researchers across the TURNkey project. Following discussions with the EC Project Officer through NORSAR, the timescale for delivery of the PAR cycle reports has been changed to months 22 (PAR Cycle 1), 30 (PAR Cycle 2 – this report) and 36 (PAR Cycle 3). The relationship between the PAR methodology and the development of the FWCR platform is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Relationship between the PAR cycles and the TURNkey FWCR development cycles

PAR cycle	Timeline	TRL	TURNkey FWCR platform
I	M18-M22	3-4	Version 1.0
II	M23-M28	4	Version 2.0
III	M28-M32	5	Final Version

The PAR model (based on three cycles of PAR) used in the TURNkey project is shown in Figure 3, below.

Figure 3 The TURNkey PAR process model

As shown in Figure 3 above, each PAR cycle comprises four research stages:

1. Validation of the (evolving) concept model from both a technical and end-user (socio-economic) perspective.
2. Testing of the conceptual model with representative end-user stakeholders.
3. Evaluation of the feedback from end-user stakeholders to inform the development of operational models and tools
4. Reflection on the degree to which the TURNkey FWCR platform is achieving its stated goal (convergence) and identifying issues that need to be addressed during the next development cycle.

3 Brief Review of PAR Cycle 1

3.1 Overview PAR Cycle 1

The first step of PAR Cycle 1 was to validate the original TURNkey project concept model (see Figure 4), outlined in the TURNkey project proposal. The original concept model provided an overview of the goal of the TURNkey project. It also outlined the theoretical considerations that were used to shape the initial TURNkey FWCR platform solution. The next steps in PAR Cycle 1 were to test the proposed solution with potential end-users, evaluate this end-user feedback to inform the development of operational models and tools and, finally, to reflect on the extent to which the (evolving) platform was achieving its stated goal of fostering urban resilience to earthquakes in Europe. For PAR Cycle 1, TURNkey researchers conducted face to face and virtual workshops and a questionnaire survey with potential end-users of the platform as well as with TURNkey scientists and engineers. This research indicated that the original TURNkey concept model was valid and could form the basis of an FWCR platform to support improved earthquake resilience across Europe. Throughout PAR cycle 1, the concept model was further refined so as to provide input into the development of the TURNkey FWCR platform version 2.0. This resulted (in May 2020) in a high-level TURNkey proposition, depicted below in Figure 5.

PAR Cycle 1 found that, whilst the theoretical basis of the tools that underpin the FWCR platform was sound, not all features desired by end-users were feasible from a scientific or engineering point of view - or would be realized by the end of the project. As a result, some changes were made to specific end-user use cases, which have been outlined in section 3.2. Figure 6 shows evolving views (in March 2021) as to what TURNkey would deliver in terms of OEF, EEW and RRE against a seismic event timeline, from long before an earthquake, to shortly before an earthquake to during an earthquake to immediately after an earthquake.

Figure 4 The original TURNkey concept model (source: TURNkey Grant Agreement)

3.2 Changes made to use cases

The original use cases were published in D1.3 and D1.4. At the end of PAR Cycle 1, revised versions of these use cases were published in D2.6. Below, the report provides an overview of the changes made to the original use cases (from D1.3 and D1.4) in D2.6. The revised use cases for OEF, EEW and RRE have been mapped against the seismic timeline in Figure 5 below.

3.2.1 Civil protection and first responder use cases

1. During PAR Cycle 1, the consensus was that, whilst it is technically feasible to provide a platform feature that makes it possible to drill down for detail on a specific area, element of

infrastructure or critical building, this feature will not be realized before the end of the project. Participants highlighted that it could be done in advance at the level of the neighbourhood – but not for every single building. The use case ‘*capturing and integrating multiple sources of information meaningfully and effectively*’ for civil protection and first responders was amended to reflect this.

2. During PAR Cycle 1, a feasibility study was being conducted in the mobile testbed, TB8, to assess the scientific/engineering feasibility of realizing aftershock alerts to first responders via the platform. At the time, TURNkey scientists rated this feasibility as 2 (on a scale of 0 to 5, whereby 0 is impossible and 5 is definitely). The use case ‘*improved visibility of danger to first responders in the field*’ for civil protection and first responders was amended to reflect this.
3. During PAR Cycle 1, the consensus was that whilst feasible from a scientific/engineering perspective, it is not part of TURNkey’s focus to show the evolution of the rescue operation or support prioritisation exercises. The use case ‘*better communication and coordination of efforts across all institutions involved in the response*’ for civil protection and first responders was amended to reflect this.

3.2.2 Business and Critical Infrastructure Use Cases

4. During PAR Cycle 1, the consensus was that, whilst feasible from a scientific/engineering perspective, TURNkey will NOT facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems as part of this project. As such, there will be NO integration with systems that control vulnerable or dangerous assets. Nor will there be integration with personal alerts carried by individual workers. (However, the latter could potentially use the TURNkey app, designed for first responders). *Business and critical infrastructure use cases for EEW were amended to reflect this.* (except for one that relied on manual control). TURNkey scientists rated the scientific/engineering feasibility of realizing such integration as 5 (on a scale of 0 to 5, whereby 0 is impossible and 5 is definitely). As such, integration with automated in-house business systems may be done in the future after the project. This would bring the platform to TRL7.
5. During PAR Cycle 1, the consensus was that issuing forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe is not yet possible, scientifically. This meant that TURNkey cannot issue the “all clear” after ground shaking. Instead, the platform can provide a notification confirming (or not) that an earthquake has happened (with probabilities) and if so, provide regular updates regarding aftershocks (with probabilities). Managers have to issue the ‘all clear’ based on this information. *All business and critical infrastructure use cases for EEW were amended to reflect this.*
6. Because issuing forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe is not yet possible, TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., “red forecast for the next 48 hours”). Instead, TURNkey can issue real-time updates of changes in seismic hazard and risk to business assets for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties. *All business and critical infrastructure use cases for OEF were amended to reflect this.*
7. During PAR Cycle 1, the dominant view was that TURNkey would provide EEW and OEF to critical infrastructure providers *indirectly via civil protection*. This meant these organisations would not be able to use TURNkey to plan and coordinate disaster management actions with their critical business partners (as the latter would not have access). The use case *joint planning: reduce the impact of operational downtime on customers* for business and critical infrastructure was amended to reflect this.

3.2.3 The revised TURNkey model

Figure 5 below shows the developing TURNkey platform prototype as it was in May 2020.

Figure 5 The TURNkey proposition (May 2020)

Figure 6 Revised use cases mapped against OEF/EEW/RRE timeline (March 2021)

NB. At the end of PAR Cycle 2 it was clarified that TURNkey will not provide 'long term OEF', only OEF after an earthquake event (i.e., for additional shocks).

4 Introduction To PAR Cycle 2

The aim of the PAR Cycle 2 was to present the second iteration of the conceptual model, technical tools, information products and user interface (which was not available during PAR Cycle 1) to end-user stakeholders – and then to evaluate and reflect on their feedback and input with TURNkey scientists and engineers towards the further development of the TURNkey FWCR platform. PAR Cycle 2 lasted from January 2021 to November 2021. Due to the travel restrictions imposed as a result of the current COVID pandemic, workshops/meetings with end-users were conducted online using digital media. A virtual demonstrator was developed to show the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform across a typical earthquake sequence (before, during – the period between an earthquake event and ground shaking reaching the end-user, and after an earthquake). It showed end-users how the platform could be used for OEF, EEW and RRE. To this end, the demonstrator explained the background to the different aspects of the TURNkey FWCR Platform and presented alternative approaches that could be used to provide OEF, EEW and RRE information as part of the TURNkey Dashboard.

The virtual demonstrator comprised 5 short video segments:

- Introduction to TURNkey;
- The TURNkey concept model;
- Operational Earthquake Forecasting;
- Earthquake Early Warning;
- Rapid Response to Earthquakes.

Each video segment used a combination of graphics/data (which together provide information) from the TURNkey Work Packages and dashboard to test end-users understanding of the information presented and of its usefulness in decision-making for disaster risk reduction and improved earthquake resilience.

The virtual demonstrator was integrated into a series of virtual workshops with civil protection, emergency responders, critical infrastructure providers and business organisations to test their response to the second conceptual model, technical tools and user interface as well as explore how the TURNkey FWCR Platform could be integrated into the revised end-user use-cases developed at the end of the PAR Cycle 1.

The results of the virtual workshops were shared with all TURNkey researchers through the regular WP meetings (WP3, WP4 and WP5) and as part of the 2nd General Assembly meeting; where the use-cases were revised to represent researchers' reflection on the models and tools developed to date. The final development of the models and tools continued in the technical work packages after the General Assembly and the final version of the conceptual model was developed through detailed discussions between WP2 researchers, WP leads, Beta 80 and NORSAR.

The final version of the conceptual model will in turn guide the development of the final version of the TURNkey FWCR platform to be delivered during this project, through PAR Cycle 3.

5 Development of the Virtual Demonstrator

The original intention for the PAR Cycle 2 was to take an early prototype of the TURNkey FWCR platform into the field to demonstrate its functionality with typical representative stakeholders from selected testbeds. In-person planned visits were replaced by virtual meetings due to the pandemic restrictions. The easiest solution at that time to demonstrate the functionality of the platform was to prepare a set of virtual demonstrators that could allow researchers to explore the usefulness of the TURNkey FWCR platform against a range of potential applications. As such a decision to develop the demonstrators was taken and ratified by the TURNkey management committee. The demonstrators were developed in such a way that they could be easily integrated into a virtual workshop environment in which TURNkey researchers could use the demonstrators as a tool to facilitate a focused discussion around the usefulness of the TURNkey FWCR platform. The TURNkey virtual demonstrators were developed between January 2021 and March 2021. The virtual workshops were held between April and May 2021. This section of the deliverable describes the development and testing of the demonstrators prior to their use in the workshops.

5.1 Developing the virtual demonstrators in Camtasia

The virtual demonstrator was developed using desktop technology provided by Tech Smith Camtasia (Figure 7). Camtasia is a software suite specifically developed for creating and recording video presentations for use in demonstration or training situations. Camtasia comprises a viewing area, media bin and multiple timelines that allow audio, video and graphical media (animations and static images) to be positioned on a virtual stage. The different types of media can either be imported from existing files, or created as bespoke media within the Camtasia software. Camtasia version 20.0.12 was used to develop the TURNkey FWCR platform demonstrators. A RODE desktop microphone was used to record high-quality audio files (model type NT-USB) and Audacity version 2.4.2 was used to edit the audio files prior to their inclusion into the Camtasia suite. This combination provided an acceptable level of quality for the development of the virtual demonstrators.

The first prototype demonstrator also included video narration which was captured using a Logitech webcam camera. Whilst the video narration was technically acceptable, it became clear during discussions with the wider PAR team that the video narration was distracting from the main messages being presented in the virtual demonstrator. It was also unclear exactly what additional functionality having a video talking headshot actually added to the message the demonstrator was trying to convey. As the demonstrator was not attempting to show the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform in real time it was concluded that there was no need to show anything other than screenshots of the dashboard (GUI).

As such, video was not included in the final versions of the demonstrator.

Figure 7 TechSmith Camtasia Software Suite

Following discussions of the potential benefits of using virtual demonstrators, including presentations of a trial demonstrator, it was agreed that 5 short demonstrators would be developed:

- a demonstrator that explained the background to the TURNkey project;
- a demonstrator that explained the TURNkey concept model;
- a demonstrator that explained how TURNkey would present operational earthquake forecasting;
- a demonstrator that explained how TURNkey will present earthquake early warning; and
- a demonstrator that explained how TURNkey would support rapid response to earthquakes.

Wherever possible the demonstrators would use real images and screenshots taken from TURNkey deliverables (provided by work packages) or from the TURNkey graphical user interface (GUI) that was being developed. (During PAR Cycle 2, the GUI was still in the early stages of development and, as such, could not be directly used to demonstrate TURNkey to end-users). If real images and screenshots were not available, surrogate images were used. Such images were either purchased from stock items available online, or extracted from other publicly available sources (in this case the images were referenced back to the source documents). In this way, it was possible to develop a series of demonstrators that reflected the current state of development of the TURNkey FWCR platform or show examples of the proposed developments that were currently under construction.

In January 2021 full development of the TURNkey FWCR platform demonstrators began. The first stage of the process was to develop a narrative storyboard for each of the demonstrators. The narrative was compiled following a review of the deliverables from TURNkey work packages and discussions between the virtual demonstrator developer (a researcher from ARU) and the TURNkey technical work package leads, including the work package responsible for developing the TURNkey FWCR platform GUI.

Due to the wide range of knowledge levels about OEF, EEW and RRE of the selected audience of the demonstrators, i.e. the stakeholders involved in the second PAR cycle, it was decided that the demonstrator would be designed to allow the researcher administering the interview/workshop to provide more explanation as and when required. As such it was decided not to use quizzes/questionnaires (as was originally intended) in favour of an open interview guide-based approach (see Appendix B) during which the researcher administering the workshop could pause the demonstrator at any time to provide more technical details or answer specific questions.

The pilot versions of the 5 virtual demonstrators (distributed in MP4 format) were tested and validated by TURNkey researchers. In particular, the TURNkey technical work package leads along with NORSAR (who were developing the scientific engine), Beta80 (who were developing the graphical user interface) and Nutcracker Research (who were conducting interviews with civil protection and emergency responders), were sent copies of the demonstrators and asked to review them for technical accuracy and presentation style. The reviewers are asked to identify any errors in the narrative (and indicate the timestamp in the video where the inaccuracy occurred) and suggest improvements to the narrative that could help better explain the TURNkey concepts. Following the review, a final set of demonstrators were produced in March 2021. Again, the final set of virtual demonstrators were circulated to the same TURNkey partners for a final validation check before the development of the final production versions of the demonstrators in mid-March 2021. The final versions of the demonstrators were accepted as a true reflection of the position of the TURNkey FWCR platform as of March 2021 by the TURNkey Management Board. The final production virtual demonstrators were:

- **Demonstrator 1 - Welcome to TURNkey.** The video outlined the impact that recent earthquakes had on Europe. The video explained the background to the TURNkey FWCR platform and explained how the other demonstrator videos would address issues of operational earthquake forecasting, earthquake early warning and rapid response to earthquakes. The video further explained how the researcher would use the demonstrators to facilitate a discussion about the TURNkey FWCR platform. In particular, the researcher would ask the audience-stakeholder for their understanding of the information TURNkey presents, if it is useful to their organisation and how they might use the information in day to day activities of their organisation, and if they have any suggestions for improving the way TURNkey presents information. Finally, the video provided assurances about how the data collected will be handled and acknowledges the EU Horizon 2020 funding. The video lasted 2 minutes 13 seconds.
- **Demonstrator 2 - The TURNkey concept model.** The video presented the original TURNkey concept model and explained that the platform consisted of a scientific engine and a graphical user interface. The video scrolled through each part of the concept model. The video explained the relationship between the TURNkey motion sensor and existing motion networks, mobile apps and eyewitness reporting. The video explained that all the data collected would be integrated into a cloud-based solution that would generate operational earthquake forecasts, issue earthquake early warning and following an earthquake will monitor its real-time impact. The forecasts, early warnings and post-earthquake information would be available to technical stakeholders to better prepare and manage their earthquake disaster response and non-technical stakeholders (including the general public) to help them better recover from the earthquake event. The video lasted 1 minute 47 seconds
- **Demonstrator 3 - Operational Earthquake Forecasts.** The video described the role of operational earthquake forecasting and explained that an operational earthquake forecast is not an earthquake prediction but a probabilistic based assessment of an earthquake occurring at a given time, in a given location and of a given magnitude. The video used screenshot examples of operational earthquake forecasting systems taken from the TURNkey FWCR platform and showed how the platform would issue a warning and how it would direct the user to a simulation forecast of its potential impact on human physical and financial losses. The platform would issue a red, amber or green warning for individual buildings or assets and would allow the user to send

messages to individuals that could be affected by the earthquake. Finally, the video presented a range of options for presenting operational earthquake forecast data and asked the user for their thoughts on the usefulness of each. The video lasted 2 minutes 30 seconds.

- **Demonstrator 4 - Earthquake Early Warning.** The video described earthquake early warning and presented a very brief overview of the science underpinning the issuing of a warning, including warning thresholds. The video showed examples of different earthquake early systems from around the world and suggested a range of warning times that could be achieved. The video then described the type of actions that individuals or systems could take to protect themselves and their property. The video presented screenshots from the TURNkey FWCR platform to show the type of information that would be provided by the platform and the method used to issue an earthquake early warning alert to an end-user. The video explained that this information would be regularly updated in the period immediately following an earthquake event, including explaining how the TURNkey FWCR platform would monitor after-shocks. Finally, the video presented a range of options for displaying earthquake early warning information, including shake maps and GIS maps showing particular built assets that may be at risk of serious damage and asked the user for their thoughts on the usefulness of each. The video lasted 2 minutes 6 seconds.
- **Demonstrator 5 - Rapid Response to Earthquakes.** The video outlined the benefits of rapid response to earthquakes to improve the speed of recovery. The video presented a series of screenshots from the TURNkey FWCR platform showing how the platform would provide information and coordinate communication (through predefined or bespoke emails sent to specific individuals or groups) to recovery teams to help them initiate recovery plans. The platform would provide a series of actions to be implemented if the earthquake exceeded pre-set threshold levels and would monitor what actions had been taken. In addition to pre-set actions, the TURNkey FWCR platform would allow individuals to generate bespoke actions in response to the actual situation on the ground and would allow eyewitness reports (from trusted users) of actual damage to be uploaded onto the system via the mobile app. The mobile app would allow users to generate observations on the level of damage and functional performance of a built asset and include a photograph of the damage. The TURNkey platform would provide a dashboard of estimates of damage (and potential recovery time) to the general building stock, to critical infrastructure and high priority buildings, and the general public. The final part of the rapid response system concerns after-shocks. The TURNkey FWCR platform would provide after-shock warning, in the form of advance notice of ground shaking via a dashboard and mobile app. Individuals who had the app would be asked to confirm that they are safe once ground shaking has stopped. If the system does not receive an 'I'm Safe' message it would alert the control centre. Finally, the video asked the user for their thoughts on the usefulness of the rapid response to earthquakes (RRE) dashboard and app. The video lasted 4 minutes 8 seconds.

Each of these demonstrators was produced in an MP4 format for the use of field researchers in workshops that took place in April/May 2021. Full transcripts of each of the demonstrator videos along with key screenshots of the graphics used are given in Appendix A. Workshops with Civil Protection, Emergency Responders and Citizens are presented by NTC in D2.10.

6 Workshops with Critical Infrastructure and Business Organisations

6.1 Methods

As outlined, in April and May 2021, ARU researchers conducted online fieldwork and analysed the results for PAR Cycle 2. ARU used a qualitative approach, which consisted of online in-depth interviews with individual respondents - as well as with pairs of respondents based at the same organisation. The interviews lasted 90 minutes and were conducted with potential end-users of the TURNkey platform. ARU interviewed critical infrastructure providers as well as civil protection staff. All of TURNkey's

geographical testbeds were covered by ARU and NTC: Iceland, France, Netherlands (ARU), Romania, Italy, Greece (NTC). As discussed, the interviews were conducted on the basis of a virtual demonstrator described in the previous section (see Appendix A) and a detailed interview guide (see Appendix B). The virtual demonstrator consisted of the five video clips described in the previous section, presenting the TURNkey proposition and the information the platform would provide for OEF, EEW and RRE. The virtual demonstrator had been designed by researchers at ARU on the basis of the findings of the 1st PAR cycle. The interview guide had been designed and pilot tested by NTC. Respondents in Iceland, France and the Netherlands were interviewed in English and Dutch, respectively.

The aim of PAR Cycle 2 was to explore different approaches to presenting the results of the TURNkey FWCR platform to the end-users and to begin to explore how the results from the TURNkey FWCR platform could be integrated into resilience and disaster management planning (in conjunction with Task 7.3). The initial findings of PAR Cycle 2 were presented to consortium research partners at the TURNkey annual meeting on 16.06.21 for expert feedback and input: an essential step in PAR. This included an initial analysis of the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) that mark the platform, discussed below.

Figure 8: The virtual demonstrator

The findings of the online qualitative interviews with TURNkey stakeholders based on the virtual demonstrator and presented in the TURNkey annual meeting are presented below.

6.2 Findings

6.2.1 How would Critical Infrastructure & General Business use OEF?

On the basis of the virtual demonstrator and interview guide, TURNkey researchers discussed with potential end-users based at three (privately run) critical infrastructure providers, as well as civil

protection (in the TBs Iceland, France and the Netherlands) how a general business or critical infrastructure provider would use OEF information in business continuity and disaster management planning. These discussions were premised on the original idea that OEF would also be provided before the (first) main shock – and not only afterwards to inform stakeholders about the probability of additional ground shaking.

Table 2 Overview respondents

Respondent	Organisation	Role	Practical / applied understanding of earthquake hazards
1 [male]	A [telecommunications]	Senior Management	Advanced
2 [male]	B [ICT infrastructure]	High-Level Technical Specialist	Advanced
3 [male]	C [rail company]	Senior Management	Good
4 [male]	D [civil protection]	Operational Specialist First Response	Good
5 [female]	D [civil protection]	Strategic Advisor	Good
6 [male]	E [factory]	High-Level Technical Specialist	Solid

The organisations in these TBs had mature disaster management plans and their assets had been built to standards conforming to the relevant building codes. Below follows an overview of the actions they would take if they received OEF information (through push or pull) which forecasted a *high probability* of significant ground shaking. What counts as ‘high’ or ‘significant’ varied by country and by organisation, as discussed below. The organisations would take the following steps, in order:

- 1) Hold a security meeting
- 2) Raise the security level in the organisation for awareness
- 3) Adjust business processes (e.g., a rail company would implement speed restrictions)
- 4) Conduct a scan of their sites to check if everything is secured, stable and ready
- 5) Assess how customers would be affected
- 6) Check that redundancy in their systems could be quickly activated
- 7) Send equipment and teams out to be prepared so as to recover faster if something happens

This information is reflected in the generic use case for OEF and simulations in section 6.3. This generic use case was presented to TURNkey scientists and engineers during workshops in June and October. During these workshops, the feedback from end-user stakeholders was evaluated to inform further development of TURNkey tools and applications. It also fed into a SWOT analysis of the platform which served to guide reflection on the degree to which the TURNkey FWCR platform was achieving its goals (described below in section 8.) As a result of these evaluations and reflections with TURNkey scientists and engineers, the relevant use cases were further developed. The latest renditions are found in section 14.

6.2.2 How would Critical Infrastructure & General Business use EEW?

TURNkey researchers discussed with the same stakeholders how a general business or critical infrastructure provider would use EEW alerts in disaster management. Their responses require TURNkey to issue EEW directly to such organisations and rely on the integration of TURNkey with automated in-house systems (such as alert systems). (Neither will be realized by the end of the project, as shown in Appendix G). However, in the hypothetical scenario that a critical infrastructure provider or general business would receive EEW alerts directly through the platform, they would set things up so that the following actions would be triggered automatically:

- Issue alerts to staff working in hazardous locations
- Issue alerts to staff operating hazardous equipment/vehicles (e.g., a rail company would alert operators to slow down trains)
- Automatically let vulnerable or hazardous systems stop or fail-safe

Stakeholders emphasized that after triggering these automated actions, business and critical infrastructure providers *would turn to established authorities* for information and RRE support.

6.2.3 How would Critical Infrastructure & General Business use RRE?

TURNkey researchers discussed with the same stakeholders how a general business or critical infrastructure provider would use TURNkey's RRE features in disaster management - and for business continuity - during and after an earthquake disaster event.

Stakeholders pointed out that for the immediate response phase (for example when factories or mass transit vehicles need to be evacuated) the organisations' current disaster management plans rely on authorities and first responders. To this end, many organisations already send automated pre-set messages to authorities and other important stakeholders. As such, in many instances, TURNkey's RRE feature to send automated pre-set messages to core stakeholders duplicates legacy systems. Three of TURNkey's RRE features were flagged as being very useful to critical infrastructure and general business stakeholders:

- The 'safety check' feature designed for first responders would also be useful for managers monitoring the wellbeing of employees who are assessing the impact of ground shaking on assets and structures, especially if those structures are hazardous (e.g., tunnels).
- Regular updates on the probability of significant aftershocks would help organisations assess the need for ongoing mitigation actions.
- Many general businesses and critical infrastructure providers already use automated preplanned actions (e.g., re-routing) in times of disaster. As these organisations have full control over their assets and sites (*unlike civil protection or first responders*) this RRE feature may be more useful for general business and critical infrastructure providers than for civil protection or first responders.

Regarding TURNkey's role in supporting *business continuity* during and after an earthquake disaster event, stakeholders highlighted that this would be facilitated primarily by the platform's *OEF and EEW* features (and not its RRE features) – as the former would enable organisations to identify and undertake the required mitigation actions needed to ensure a rapid restoration of business processes and supply chains.

6.2.4 Where should TURNkey sit?

TURNkey researchers discussed with the same stakeholders who they believed should have direct access to and control over TURNkey information in a given region. There was a general consensus that the public should not have direct access to OEF, EEW or RRE information for the following three reasons:

- 1) Stakeholders emphasized the need for consistent messaging to the public regarding earthquake hazards and disasters. They were concerned that TURNkey information might at times contradict official sources (e.g., Met office, Civil Protection) and result in public confusion.
- 2) They also expressed concern that TURNkey information might be misunderstood by the public and cause unnecessary anxiety.
- 3) Finally, they expressed concern that false positives or negatives issued by TURNkey might undermine public trust in the platform.

Because stakeholders strongly felt that the general public should not have access to TURNkey information for the above reasons, they also believed that general businesses should not be given direct access, as these organisations are an integral part of the general public. They expressed the view that direct access to TURNkey information should be restricted to public authorities, first responders and critical infrastructure providers. However, they flagged that even within these organisations access should be highly restricted to prevent unauthorized information from ending up in the public domain. They highlighted that employees based at these organisations are also members of the general public and expressed the concern that they might publicly share information they had misunderstood, resulting in public confusion and unnecessary anxiety.

6.2.5 Who should control public EEW and OEF messaging?

Stakeholders highlighted that in their TBs (Iceland, France, Netherlands) civil protection, the national seismological institute and/or Met office are generally trusted by the public to provide reliable information and warnings about natural hazards. To ensure consistent public messaging, the stakeholders expressed the view that public EEW and OEF communications should be centrally controlled by these authorities. However, as outlined, stakeholders also saw the benefits of critical infrastructure having direct access to OEF and EEW information, as this would enable them to take mitigation actions and alert staff. They highlighted that, especially with heavy industry (e.g., large chemical plants) such mitigation actions would prevent incidents and unburden first responders during RRE. As such, the consensus was that whilst a region would benefit from critical infrastructure providers having direct access to EEW and OEF, the public messaging of this information should be centrally controlled by public authorities (e.g., civil protection).

6.2.6 Who should control RRE information?

In line with the above, stakeholders also expressed the view that public RRE communications should be centrally controlled by the before-mentioned public authorities. Again, to ensure consistent messaging to the public, they stated that public RRE messaging should be undertaken by designated spokespeople based at these public authorities only. The critical infrastructure providers who were interviewed made it clear that they themselves would not want to use the TURNkey platform to send automated messages about earthquake events to the general public. This includes automated messages to their general customers about possible service disruption. As outlined, they already send automated messages to their business customers (e.g., supply chain) and general authorities in times of disaster. Stakeholders stated that, in their view, civil protection (should) have the overall picture of a disaster

event and (should) be primarily responsible for organizing a response. As such, there was consensus that public RRE messaging should be controlled by civil protection.

Stakeholders also saw the benefits of critical infrastructure having access to RRE information, especially during the early recovery phase. When it came to the immediate response phase, they saw the value of triggering automated pre-planned actions. Indeed, as outlined, critical infrastructure providers already do this in times of disaster. However, beyond this, stakeholders were unclear on how TURNkey's RRE information could support them in their *immediate* response efforts. They pointed out that – for example - evacuating a factory or a mass transit vehicle is a science in itself and requires advanced planning and training. They did not think that TURNkey's RRE information would add value during this immediate phase (beyond triggering automated actions). Their current response plans for the immediate period after ground shaking rely on assistance from civil protection and first responders. However, when it came to the early recovery phase stakeholders noted the value of receiving updates on the probability of additional ground shaking, as this would be useful for mitigation actions. For example, if the probability of further ground shaking remained high, they might delay restarting their facilities at full capacity (or restarting their machinery/vehicles at full speed). They also saw value in the safety check feature. This would be useful for staff inspecting (potentially) damaged structures after an earthquake event. As such, it would add value for critical infrastructure providers to have direct access to RRE information, specifically updates on the probability of further ground shaking, alerts (that could be integrated into automated systems) and the 'I'm safe' feature. However, as before, the consensus was that whilst a region would benefit from critical infrastructure providers having access to RRE information, the public messaging of this information should be centrally controlled by public authorities (e.g., civil protection).

6.2.7 One size does not fit all

In interviews stakeholders highlighted how the organisational and country context of their organisations affected when and how the TURNkey platform could add value to their mitigation and response efforts. They flagged that the disaster management systems, structures and policies that were already in place (both nationally and within their organisations) shaped if and how TURNkey would be used to prepare for - and respond to - earthquake events. In doing so, they highlighted the need for both customization and integration with existing systems.

6.2.8 Country Context

To illustrate the above, this section will now compare two of TURNkey's TBs: Iceland and the Netherlands. In each country, the risk of casualties during an earthquake event is very low. However, the reasons for this are very different. Iceland is one of the most earthquake-prone countries in the world because it straddles two of the Earth's tectonic plates. During the last major earthquake (in Hveragerði, 2008) 30 people lost their lives. Minor earthquakes are common in Iceland and critical infrastructure is built to withstand even major ones. In the Netherlands, earthquakes result primarily from gas extraction. They damage structures (e.g., residential buildings) primarily because these structures were not designed with earthquakes in mind. Annually, five people die in the Netherlands due to earthquakes. However, they do not die as a result of physical injuries: they die as a result of stress caused by the hazard. Whereas in the Netherlands a M3 earthquake is considered to be very high, in Iceland this level of risk is completely normalized. In the Netherlands, one of the key concerns of public authorities in the context of earthquakes is public mental health. As such, they stress the need to carefully manage earthquake information and are concerned about private or independent earthquake platforms that are outside of their control. In Iceland, a M3 earthquake is a minor event. Because residential buildings and heavy industry are designed to withstand major earthquakes, M3 ground shaking is no cause for significant concern. Iceland benefits from comprehensive and advanced national disaster management systems. Furthermore, critical infrastructure providers have mature

disaster management and business continuity plans, which have been designed to mitigate earthquake hazards. Given this high baseline for earthquake preparedness, OEF before the first (main) shock is not as valuable to Icelandic organisations as it would be to organisations located elsewhere. This form of OEF would have been valuable to Dutch organisations. However, because gas extraction is being phased out, funding and political buy-in for new earthquake mitigation and response platforms are waning. This means that the opportunities and barriers to the uptake and use of TURNkey are very different in each country. It was clarified at the end of PAR Cycle 2 that TURNkey would only provide OEF after an earthquake event, to inform stakeholders about the probability of additional ground shaking.

Figure 9 Iceland and The Netherlands

6.2.9 Organisational Context

In addition to the national context, the context and nature of a critical infrastructure provider itself also shape when and how the TURNkey FWCR platform could add value to their mitigation and response efforts. To illustrate this, this report will now compare a state-of-the-art factory with a mass transit company. In this example, the production processes of the factory need to be kept going 24/7. Stopping the production process for any period of time seriously damages the equipment. As a state-of-the-art factory, all structures and equipment have been built to the highest standard. The factory has full control over its assets and structures which are all on site - and all vulnerable or hazardous systems are routinely checked. Furthermore, mature disaster management plans are in place and staff regularly perform drills. Whilst TURNkey would still offer value to this factory (e.g., by facilitating automated actions) it would be less valuable than for a different type of organisation. This is because the factory (and production) will likely be unaffected by significant ground shaking due to the mitigation measures that are already in place. In addition, stopping production is likely to cost more than for the plant to just keep going. As such, it would not be helpful for TURNkey to automatically shut down the process.

The situation is different for a mass transit company, responsible for transporting persons. In this example, the transit company does not have full control over the assets and structures it uses (e.g., roads, rail track) to provide its services. They are publicly accessible, massive and subject to sudden unexpected problems (e.g., fallen trees). Whilst earthquake mitigation is also an integral part of the standard operating procedures of this company, EEW and OEF would add significant extra value. OEF warnings would enable the company to perform extra checks, impose speed restrictions or close down routes as a precaution. EEW would enable the company to slow down its vehicles, reducing the risk of casualties. As such, the opportunities and barriers to the uptake and use of TURNkey are very different for different types of critical infrastructure providers.

6.2.10 Challenges to be addressed

Stakeholders listed a number of barriers and challenges TURNkey needs to address before these potential end-users would consider adopting the platform. These challenges fall into three categories: challenges related to data security; challenges related to integration; and challenges related to persuasion. They have been listed below in the form of questions asked of the platform by end-user stakeholders.

6.2.10.1 *Organisations need clarity on data security and data privacy*

Stakeholders needed clarity on how TURNkey would handle data security and data privacy issues. They needed answers to the following questions:

- What information will TURNkey collect from business systems and smartphones?
- What other systems would TURNkey have access to?
- How else could this information be used (e.g., could it be used to monitor/spy on organisations or people?)
- Could TURNkey put organisations at risk of cyber-attacks?
- What are the security risks to organisations of a Cloud-based system?

6.2.10.2 *Integration Challenges*

Stakeholders needed clarity on how TURNkey would fit with existing systems and processes. They needed answers to the following questions:

- Organisations currently operate based on information provided by official authorities. How would the information provided by TURNkey fit into this?
- Countries have established (mandated) disaster management systems and protocols. How could the TURNkey platform be integrated into these structures?
- Organisations have existing technical systems and disaster management processes. How could the TURNkey platform be integrated into these structures?

6.2.10.3 *Examples of Persuasion Challenges*

Finally, stakeholders put forward a number of challenges TURNkey needs to address. They needed answers to the following questions:

- IT is one of the top costs for organisations today. What is the value of TURNkey over the other forecasts that are already available?
- Organisations have established systems for doing things and they want to keep working at speed. They don't want any 'fuss' or 'distractions'. Why should they spend precious time on adopting and learning a new system?
- Organisations already have a lot of apps and systems that never get used. They don't want extra stuff. Wouldn't a new platform just be a waste of money?
- Would people remember to use TURNkey? Earthquakes are not that frequent. Wouldn't the system just gather dust?

6.3 Generic use-cases for business and critical infrastructure developed through the 2nd PAR cycle

The results from the interviews were used to refine the use cases developed in the PAR Cycle 1 to produce a set of generic use cases that reflected the state of the TURNkey FWCR platform in June 2021. The generic use cases represented the first attempt by the TURNkey project to move from specific examples given by those interviewed in the testbeds to a generic set of use cases that could be applicable more widely across different critical infrastructure and business organisations. The generic use cases were also used as the basis for the development of a series of theoretical models linking the potential application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to improved organisational resilience (reported in D5.3) and, in combination with the operational considerations outlined in section 6.2, will inform the development of the disaster management plan (DMP) and business continuity and resiliency plan (BCRP) for the business models being developed in Task 7.3.

6.3.1 Generic use-cases business and CI, before the earthquake event (main event or aftershock)

Findings – Generic use cases business and critical infrastructure (confirmed/updated June 2021)		
Personal safety	To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking	Adjust/Reschedule non-time-critical tasks during periods of high earthquake risk [OEF for additional shocks]
		Check earthquake risk management/health and safety protocols are in place and working as expected [Simulations]
Business Disruption	Activation of off-site backup	Test physical/data off-site backup systems and onsite redundancy systems (e.g. local, power generators) functionality during an earthquake event [Simulations]
		Assess the potential impact of disruption on customers during an earthquake event [Simulations]
Joint planning	Reduce the impact of operational downtime	Activation of the disaster planning committee to test disaster management and business continuity plans and place response teams on high alert during a period of high earthquake risk [OEF for additional shocks]

TURNkey Platform

Before an Earthquake Event

Improved Resilience

6.3.2 Generic use-cases business and CI, during the earthquake event

Findings – Generic business and CI use cases (confirmed/updated June 2021)		
Use Case	Goal	Use Case Instance
Personal Safety	To avoid/reduce the risk of injury to employees and/or customers	Automatic alert to employees/customers to drop, cover, hold
		Automatic alert to employees operating hazardous equipment to stop the process or to initiate shut down
Community safety	To avoid/reduce the risk of injury to members of the public and the wider community	Automatic alert to initiate safety protocols for ongoing business processes during ground shaking
		Automatic alert to initiate safety protocols to reduce cascading impacts
Minimise Damage to Critical Systems	To reduce potential damage to critical business systems as a result of ground shaking	Automatic alert to operators of critical systems to place the systems in a 'safe mode' during ground shaking
		Automatic alert to stop vertical/horizontal transport systems at a safe location

TURNkey Platform

During an Earthquake Event

Improved Resilience

6.3.3 Generic use-cases business and CI, immediately after the earthquake event

Findings – Generic business and CI use cases (confirmed/update June 2021)		
Use Case	Goal	Use Case Instance
Resume / continue work - quickly and safely	Improved employee safety allowing rapid return to work	Early assessment of building damage states to support health and safety checks on employees undertaking on-site damage assessment (aftershock information for buildings)
		Aftershock warnings for employees undertaking assessment or repair tasks, including I'm Safe response through the mobile app
Restart / continue systems - quickly and safely	Minimise downtime of critical processes and systems	Rapid activation of standard (pre-planned) disaster response and recovery protocols, including automated emails to key employees and stakeholders
		Rapid assessment (hours) of the functionality of critical systems and processes supported and updated by real-time on-site reporting
Restart / continue business – quickly and safely	Reduce disruption to business systems and customers	Automated (pre-planned) emails to suppliers and other business customers to better manage supply chain/customer relationships
		Joint planning with community/sector stakeholders to facilitate community/sector-wide recovery plans

TURNkey Platform

After an earthquake event

Improved Resilience

7 Other Activities Carried out for PAR Cycle 2

As outlined above, PAR Cycle 2 ran from January to November 2021. During this period, researchers from ARU and NTC attended the monthly meetings of all TURNkey WPs. At these meetings, they gave regular feedback to participants on PAR activities with end-users. During the meetings for WP3 about task 3.5, it was decided that the views of end-users should be sought on how TURNkey could best present hazard information (e.g., on a map). As such, during July and August 2021, ARU and NTC conducted a survey with the same respondents who had participated in the qualitative interviews for PAR Cycle 2, as a follow-up. The survey ran from 19.07.21 to 20.08.21. It was completed by TURNkey partners from all testbeds (n.19). This was done in partnership with KNMI. The key findings of the survey were the following:

- Regarding what term expressing uncertainty stakeholders found clearest, 66% of respondents picked as their first choice the term 'probability' and 54% picked as their second choice the term 'likelihood'. Very few respondents selected the terms 'forecast' or 'chance' as either their first or second choices.
- When asked if it was useful for a hazard map to display data with three different levels of uncertainty (low, best, high), 84% said that it was either helpful or extremely helpful to have the best estimates. 53% said that it was either helpful or extremely helpful to have all three levels.
- When asked if they would prefer to toggle between the different levels of uncertainty (i.e., low, best and high) using buttons or a slider, responders expressed a slight preference for a slider (58% versus 42%).
- When asked what colour scheme they would prefer to be used on a hazard map, 68% selected the 'fire' colour scheme as their 1st or 2nd choice. Another 68% selected the less bright 'yellow-orange-red' colour scheme. The monochrome red colour scheme and the viridis colour scheme (green and blue) were not popular. Stakeholders expressed no interest in being able to define their own colour scheme.
- When asked if they would prefer to toggle the colour settings of a hazard map between an (expected) maximum value for a region and a maximum value for an earthquake, 84% said that they would want to be able to do so.
- When asked if they would prefer to set their own threshold levels for their own points of interest (e.g., the location of critical built assets) 74% stated that they would want to do so.

The detailed findings of this survey have been published in D3.12.

8 2nd SWOT Analysis TURNkey (June 2021)

The findings of general use cases (above) were presented at the TURNkey General Assembly on 16.06.2021. They informed a general discussion about the platforms Strengths Weaknesses Opportunities and Threats. This SWOT analysis constitutes a follow-up to the first SWOT analysis conducted during PAR Cycle 1, which has been published in D1.2. Due to time constraints, it was not possible to complete the SWOT analysis during the meeting. As such, after the meeting a followed up online survey (see Appendix C) was sent to all TURNkey partners about TURNkey's SWOT. The survey was completed by eleven of TURNkey's consortium partners across all work packages. The survey ran from 26.06.21 to 20.08.21. The detailed findings are presented below in Appendix D and summarised in Figure 10.

Figure 10 The TURNkey SWOT analysis, June 2021

8.1 Strengths

During the meeting and in the follow-up survey, respondents were presented with a series of features of the TURNkey FWCR platform which had been identified as strengths of the platform. The scientists and engineers who participated in the meeting and later on in the survey were asked to give their view and their opinion as to whether or not they agreed that these features were indeed strengths of the TURNkey FWCR platform. In total 15 strengths were presented to the participants. The vast majority of participants agreed with each of the strengths that had been identified previously. The only exception to this is the following:

- *TURNkey provides forecasts for cascading hazard events as part of operational earthquake forecasting.*

When it came to this particular strength, which had been identified during earlier rounds of research, only half of the participants agreed that this was indeed a strength – with half of the participants being either neutral, in disagreement or in strong disagreement that this is a strength of the TURNkey platform. The reason for this limited support is likely that whilst the TURNkey FWCR platform could facilitate assessments of cascading hazard events, the platform itself does not provide such an analysis.

All other strengths that had been identified previously were endorsed by the vast majority of participants as either strengths or key strengths. The full list of strengths and participants' assessments of them is available in Appendix D. The strengths listed below were identified by participants as the platforms' core strengths:

- *TURNkey provides an integrated system for all stages of the earthquake disaster cycle*
- *TURNkey facilitates two-way communication during the rapid response to the earthquake phase.*
- *TURNkey provides early warnings for aftershocks.*
- *TURNkey provides real-time infrastructure performance status alerts during the rapid response to the earthquake phase.*

During the SWOT analysis participants were asked to list other important strengths of TURNkey, which hadn't been identified during earlier rounds of PAR. They identified the following:

- *TURNkey integrates outputs from a scientific engine (a set of algorithms and data sets) into a platform for operational decision making, which is highly innovative.*
- *TURNkey provides EEW, OEF and RRE information to end-users about a region that goes beyond the territory they are responsible for, giving them a broader view of the hazard/disaster situation.*
- *The TURNkey scientific engine is made flexibly enough to handle various input formats. It can process both default and user-defined inputs (e.g., hazard maps, soil profile maps). This makes TURNkey highly customizable for end-users.*
- *TURNkey provides long term monitoring of buildings and infrastructures both before and after earthquake events.*
- *A final strength that was identified was the fact that TURNkey is a multinational project that unites researchers from research institutes, universities and private companies.*

All these strengths would later be explored in more detail during the workshop at NORSAR in November 2021 in the context of a hypothetical hospital scenario (see section 9). These discussions

resulted in a more nuanced understanding of these strengths and informed revisions to the use cases (see section 14).

When asked for ideas as to how TURNkey's strengths could be further exploited, respondents mentioned:

- *TURNkey's ability to handle various input formats would enable end-users to conduct a detailed study based on both prospective and retrospective scenarios so as to improve local earthquake disaster management.*
- *TURNkey strengths could be disseminated through various channels (TV, Internet, social networks) so interested people could learn about them.*

8.2 Weaknesses

Respondents were also presented with a series of features of the TURNkey FWCR platform which had been identified as weaknesses of the platform. The scientists and engineers who participated in the meeting and later on in the survey were asked to give their view and their opinion as to whether or not they agreed that these features were indeed weaknesses of the TURNkey FWCR platform. In total 13 weaknesses were presented to the participants. Only 7 of the weaknesses that had been identified previously were recognised as weaknesses by over half of the participants. Only a small group of participants recognised the other 6 features as weaknesses. The following four features were seen as weaknesses by the fewest people (less than 20%; 40% to 60% were neutral and the remainder disagreed or strongly disagreed):

- *TURNkey uses unclear technical ambiguous terminology*
- *TURNkey's cost (e.g., of sensor network maintenance)*
- *TURNkey fails to accurately model local seismic conditions*
- *The uncertainty of TURNkey's OEF information*

The 7 other weaknesses that had been identified previously were endorsed by a small majority of participants as either weaknesses or key weaknesses. The full list of weaknesses and participants' assessments of them is available in Appendix D. The weaknesses listed below were identified by participants as the platforms' core weaknesses:

- *There is no plan for long-term system maintenance or upgrades*
- *There is no business model for TURNkey*
- *TURNkey has not been validated against a wide range of operational circumstances*

During the SWOT analysis participants were asked to list other important weaknesses of TURNkey, which hadn't been identified during earlier rounds of PAR. They identified the following:

- *The computation cost of the TURNkey scientific engine (e.g., time and CPU) might be high especially for a large region with a large number of buildings and other infrastructure*
- *The TURNkey user interface has a lot of tabs and options and users might get lost in their efforts to navigate the platform and get discouraged*

As with the strengths, these weaknesses would later be explored in more detail during the workshop at NORSAR in November 2021 in the context of a hypothetical hospital scenario (see section 9).

When asked for ideas as to how TURNkey's weaknesses could be addressed, respondents mentioned:

- *For large scale computations, cloud-based parallel computing might be necessary. However, this would incur extra costs for maintenance.*
- *Concrete ways of addressing TURNkey's weaknesses might be found through discussions and collaborations among members of the team.*

8.3 Opportunities

Respondents were also presented with a series of attributes of TURNkey's external environment (e.g., market needs) which had been identified as opportunities for the platform. The scientists and engineers who participated in the meeting and later on in the survey were asked to give their view and their opinion as to whether or not they agreed that these attributes were indeed opportunities for the TURNkey FWCR platform. In total 15 opportunities were presented to the participants. The vast majority of participants agreed with each of the opportunities that had been identified previously. The only exceptions to this were the following:

- *TURNkey could improve public mental preparedness*
- *TURNkey could improve occupational mental preparedness*

This aligns with feedback from potential end-users (see section 6.2.4) who stated that TURNkey information could lead to misunderstandings and unnecessary anxiety, if made directly available to the public – or if shared (without restriction) with all employees of an organisation with direct access to TURNkey (e.g., a first responder organisation or a critical infrastructure).

All other opportunities that had been identified previously were endorsed by the vast majority of participants as either opportunities or key opportunities. The full list of opportunities and participants' assessments of them is available in Appendix D. The opportunities listed below were identified by participants as the platforms' core opportunities:

- *TURNkey could contribute to better-informed disaster resilience plans*
- *TURNkey could enable the early activation of disaster response plans*
- *TURNkey could support on-site facility control, e.g., for critical infrastructure providers*

During the SWOT analysis participants were asked to list other important opportunities for TURNkey, which hadn't been identified during earlier rounds of PAR. They identified the following:

- *The TURNkey scientific engine could easily be further developed to incorporate state of the art methods for long-term analyses*
- *The TURNkey project itself constitutes an opportunity for people to work together towards its accomplishment*
- *TURNkey could facilitate more streamlined communications between all parties involved in disaster management before, during, and after an earthquake*

All these opportunities would later be explored in more detail during the workshop at NORSAR in November 2021 in the context of a hypothetical hospital scenario (see section 9). These discussions resulted in a more nuanced understanding of these opportunities and informed revisions to the use cases (see section 14).

When asked for ideas as to how TURNkey's opportunities could be further exploited, respondents mentioned:

- *Keeping the TURNkey platform open enough to, over time, integrate new methodologies into the engine – not just during development but also in the long term when it's operational. This would yield more reliable results throughout the disaster cycle.*
- *Raising awareness of how TURNkey could address market needs through dissemination, so more people could take advantage of the platform.*

8.4 Threats

Respondents were also presented with a series of attributes of TURNkey's external environment, which had been identified as threats to the uptake or use of the platform. The scientists and engineers who participated in the meeting and later on in the survey were asked to give their view and their opinion as to whether or not they agreed that these attributes were indeed threats to the TURNkey FWCR platform. In total 13 threats were presented to the participants. The vast majority of participants agreed with each of the threats that had been identified previously. The only exceptions to this were the following:

- *TURNkey data is incompatible with existing end-user data formats, e.g., the use of colour*
- *Unfair access and governance systems*
- *A failure to reflect local end-users attitudes to risk*

Whereas the majority of respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed that the first point was a threat to TURNkey, most were neutral with regards to the last two points. As outlined in section 7, an online survey was carried out with end-users on how best to present hazard information, which was published in D3.12. Participants were aware of this work, which is likely why they rejected the first point as a threat to TURNkey.

All other threats that had been identified previously were endorsed by the vast majority of participants as either threats or key threats. The full list of threats and participants' assessments of them is available in Appendix D. The threats listed below were identified by participants as the platforms' primary threats:

- *A failure to integrate TURNkey with existing national disaster management systems and processes*
- *A failure to integrate TURNkey with existing organisational disaster management systems, etc*

Respondents did not put forward any additional threats that had not already been listed.

When asked for ideas as to how TURNkey could mitigate against its threats, respondents mentioned:

- *Ensuring that TURNkey's actions can be understood by all members of the team and by collaborators outside the project.*

9 Workshop at NORSAR 19-20 October 2021

9.1 Introduction

The workshop was held at NORSAR's offices in Lillestrom on the 19th and 20th of October 2021. Representatives from NORSAR, ARU, Nutcracker Research, Beta80 and Gempa were present. The workshop aimed to test:

- the ability of the TURNkey FWCR platform to deliver against the 2nd iteration of use cases developed following the fieldwork with end-users in March/April 2021; and
- the TURNkey FWCR platform against a set of generalised use cases applied to a hypothetical end-user scenario in preparation for the end-user demonstrator workshops planned for February/March 2022.

The workshop was organised into 4 sections

1. a review of the TURNkey FWCR platform against civil protection and emergency responder expectations (reported in D2.10);
2. a test of the TURNkey FWCR platform against a hypothetical hospital scenario;
3. a general discussion of the TURNkey FWCR platform to further inform the development of a 2nd virtual demonstrator for use in the workshops planned for task 7.3 with business and critical infrastructure organisations (to be reported in D7.7); and
4. a review of the TURNkey FWCR platform against the 2nd iteration of the use cases (reported in section 11 and Appendix G of this deliverable).

A hypothetical hospital was chosen to represent a critical infrastructure/business. The rationale for choosing a hospital scenario was the critical role hospitals play in disaster management/recovery. Furthermore, hospital operations are greatly affected by (the level and nature) physical earthquake damage.

Whilst the workshop materials designed to support the discussions were strictly linear, the team facilitated a natural and organic dialogue around the topics that were included. This section reports the findings from the discussions around the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to the hypothetical hospital scenario. The findings of the workshop are presented by topic, in a structured manner for ease of reading. The report first outlines the hospital scenario that was used to test the TURNkey FWCR platform. It then goes on to describe insights gained during this test as well as from a general discussion of the TURNkey FWCR platform, looking first at operational earthquake forecasting (OEF), then earthquake early warning (EEW) and finally at rapid response to earthquakes (RRE). Detailed notes were taken during the workshop sessions. Furthermore, they were recorded and later transcribed.

9.2 Methods

9.2.1 A test of TURNkey against a hypothetical hospital scenario.

Prior to the workshop, researchers at ARU developed the hospital scenario, which was in part based on role-play. The scenario represented a longitudinal timeline of the steps that a typical hospital would

need to take to procure, commission, operate and maintain the TURNkey FWCR platform over the period before during and after an earthquake event. The researchers who developed it were experienced in disaster risk management for business/critical infrastructure organisations, including disaster risk management for hospitals in the context of earthquakes.

9.2.2 The hypothetical hospital team

The hypothetical hospital team comprised:

- **The hospital's risk manager** who looked at the risk management aspects of applying the TURNkey FWCR platform to the hospital.
- **A representative of the hospital's operational management** who looked at the TURNkey FWCR platform from the perspective of the functional performance of the hospital.
- **A representative of the hospital's engineering consultants** who looked at the technical background to the TURNkey FWCR platform and the data that may be needed from the hospital to implement the platform.
- **A representative of the hospital's facilities management team** who looked at the potential impact of the TURNkey FWCR platform on hospital disaster management from a service delivery perspective.
- **A representative of the hospital's financial consultants** who looked at the TURNkey FWCR platform from a business case and cost-benefit perspective.
- **The hospital's project manager** who would be responsible for overseeing the implementation of the TURNkey FWCR platform should the hospital decide to implement it and looked at the TURNkey FWCR platform through this lens.

9.2.3 The hypothetical hospital scenario

Prior to the workshop, the hypothetical hospital team jointly developed a set of use cases describing how they believed the TURNkey FWCR platform could be applied to a hypothetical hospital (included in Appendix F). The hospital scenario was based on the following fictional data:

- The hospital is a general hospital providing routine services to a population of approximately 35,000 citizens. The hospital is in a highly active earthquake zone and is located near a TURNkey sensor network. It has an average bed occupancy rate of 90%. It employs 2250 staff.
- The hospital has 4 services located in discrete buildings on a single site; an emergency department, operating theatres, general wards and administration.
- As the hospital is built according to the latest earthquake design standards, the hospital wants to explore not only the potential impact of the earthquake on structural damage to each building but also on potential damage to non-structural elements that together would impact the functional performance of the hospital after an earthquake event; particularly after a minor earthquake that may not necessarily cause structural damage but could cause non-structural damage.
- Based upon the World Health Organisation Hospital Safety Index rating, the hospital is classified as very structurally sound and in a good state of repair. The only real issues of concern are the close proximity of some buildings to each other and the height variation of buildings across the site (both risk indicators in the safety index).
- The hospital has a detailed and mature disaster management plan, including an emergency disaster committee and clearly designated roles and responsibilities for those who would have to respond to an earthquake. The hospital also has coordination mechanisms that support

cooperation with local emergency/disaster management agencies and regional healthcare networks.

- The hospital has a clear evacuation plan for major disaster events that includes well-signposted routes and audible alerts that can be used to trigger an evacuation; including plans in place for vertical evacuation. The hospital has identified a safe location where those evacuated can muster. The hospital runs regular evacuation drills.

9.2.4 Issues explored during the workshop scenario

The hypothetical hospital scenario provided the background to explore the potential application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to a typical critical infrastructure organisation. The discussions centred around two meta-level questions:

1. Why should the hypothetical hospital invest time and effort in using the TURNkey FWCR platform?
2. Could the TURNkey FWCR platform help the hospital better manage its earthquake disaster risk, and if so, how?

and 5 operational issues:

1. Defining what data is required to customize the TURNkey FWCR platform to the hospital's specific needs. This was a recurring question across each stage of the earthquake sequence cycle.
2. Understanding what data or information the TURNkey FWCR platform issues in the period of time preceding, during or following a major earthquake event;
3. Understanding how this data or information is delivered to the hospitals' risk and facilities management team
4. Assessing the reliability of the data or information
5. Identifying other potential benefits of TURNkey FWCR platform for scenario planning and disaster preparedness.

9.2.5 The hospital use cases

This section provides an overview of the eight hospital use cases that were developed by the hypothetical hospital team based on their understanding of the TURNkey FWCR platform. The hospital use cases are based on the use cases developed during the PAR Cycle 1 (D2.6). The complete use cases are presented in Appendix F.

1. OEF - employee and patient safety. Twenty-three actions were identified covering a time period of 3 months, 2 weeks and 72 hours before an earthquake;
2. OEF - minimise business disruption. Twenty-two actions were identified covering a time period of 3 months, 2 weeks and 72 hours before an earthquake;
3. OEF - joint planning (e.g. with civil protection and other external agencies). Five actions were identified covering a time period of 3 months, 2 weeks and 72 hours before an earthquake;
4. EEW - safeguard employee safety. Six actions were identified covering a time period of 30 seconds and 10 seconds before ground shaking;
5. EEW - safeguarding patient (client) safety. Nine actions were identified covering a period of one minute, 30 seconds and 10 seconds before ground shaking (note: some of these actions were the same as those for safeguarding employee safety);
6. EEW - minimise damage to critical systems. Seven actions were identified covering a period of one minute, 30 seconds and 10 seconds before ground shaking;

7. RRE – enable the rapid and safe return of functional performance. Four actions were identified for the safe return of staff and patients;
8. RRE - minimise ongoing business disruption. Five actions were identified to minimise ongoing business disruption.

9.2.6 Running the scenario: a general discussion and review

The business and critical infrastructure part of the workshop lasted approximately 6 hours. The ARU team explored the application of each stage of the TURNkey FWCR platform with the software development team, covering OEF, EEW and RRE. The hypothetical hospital team followed the hospital use cases that had been developed to guide the discussions but facilitated a natural and organic dialogue around the topics that were included. This was done to reflect the temporal interaction and interrelationships that exist within the TURNkey FWCR platform. As such, the workshop methodology took the form of a semi-structured discussion around the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to the hypothetical hospital scenario; as well as to business and critical infrastructure providers more broadly.

As the aim of the workshop was to examine the practical applicability of the TURNkey FWCR platform to end-user needs, the discussions periodically needed to explore technical issues around how the TURNkey FWCR platform generates its data. These discussions were informed by issues and questions that were raised by end-users during PAR Cycle 2 as well as by the knowledge and personal experiences of the hypothetical hospital team of earthquake disaster scenarios. In particular, the reliability of operational earthquake forecasting was discussed in detail – as were the timescales for issuing earthquake early warning alerts. Whilst these discussions were only of peripheral interest to the development of the final set of use cases, they will be fundamental to the business models that are being developed in work package 7. As such, the discussions are noted here but will be analysed in detail in task 7.3 and reported in deliverable D7.7.

The next sections provide the insights gained during the hospital scenario, the general discussion and the review, structured by OEF, EEW and RRE.

9.3 Findings

9.3.1 The application of the TURNkey FWCR platform before an earthquake event

The discussion started with the software team explaining that the TURNkey FWCR platform will provide two types of information before an earthquake based on simulations:

- ***Periodic (e.g., daily) assessments of the probability of ground acceleration exceeding a given intensity threshold.*** This first type is probabilistic and based on background seismicity. It constitutes a parametric simulation based on measured geophysical parameters. It assumes heightened seismicity (i.e., an increase in the probability of certain shaking levels being exceeded). It provides risk estimates and DSS recommendations for a set of risk scenarios. Using the probabilistic background seismicity, TURNkey generates a map of changed hazard levels (if any), with the estimated impact (physical and socio-economic) and DSS. The simulation does not issue alerts (e.g., Red Amber Green).
- ***Deterministic simulations of single risk scenarios.*** This second type is deterministic and based on user-defined inputs. It assumes that an earthquake of given magnitude has occurred at given location. The details of the scenario are defined by users who can set the magnitude, location, depth and fault mechanism. Users can use this type of simulation to calculate (for example) structural damage to, or loss of, assets based on data they provide. This second type of

simulation provides risk estimates and DSS recommendations for a single risk scenario. Using user defined data, TURNkey generates a shakemap with the estimated impacts (both physical and socio-economic) and DSS. The simulation does not issue alerts (e.g., Red Amber Green). Calculations for structural damages and losses are based on user defined data (e.g., about their assets) as well generic or bespoke fragility and loss functions, which match the EMS(98) vulnerability classes and related loss functions.

Both types of simulations provide the end-user with information regarding:

- Hazard: (1) the long-term/short-term seismicity in terms of probability of exceedance certain shaking levels: or (2) an earthquake event in terms of shakemap
- Risk: physical vulnerabilities (e.g., vulnerability level, damage grade, economic loss, amount of debris, functionality for EF and CIS) and social vulnerabilities (e.g., casualty, number of homeless, number of shelters)

Furthermore, the platform provides a decision support system (DSS). However, at the time of the workshop this had not yet been integrated. The DSS is based on cost-benefit analysis for different user defined actions. It calculates the cost-benefit classes for different actions – and inactions – for the risk scenario at hand.

9.3.1.1 Using the simulations for operational purposes.

Outputs from the first type of simulation can be used to inform the second. The estimated probability of ground acceleration exceeding a given threshold can be used by the TURNkey FWCR platform to calculate estimates for both fragility and losses, in case a seismic event of such intensity occurs. These estimates can be calculated by varying the earthquake epicentre and intensity to produce estimates for PGA (Peak Ground Acceleration), and then to calculate damage states and expected losses. As outlined, the damage state of the built assets will be based on either generic or bespoke fragility and loss functions. The former is contained within the TURNkey FWCR platform scientific engine whereas the latter needs to be provided to the scientific engine by the end-user or their consultants. The scientific engine includes static libraries of fragility functions, vulnerability functions, capacity functions, loss-to-damage functions, functionality functions. These functions can be used to estimate building-level damage. To establish the typology for general buildings and essential facilities the end-user would need to input information on the building construction materials, the height and lateral resistant system. If the user can provide component-level (e.g., beam, column) information, then the analysis can be performed at this level. *However, TURNkey does not currently provide this functionality.* For critical infrastructure systems, the user would need to provide a system level definition instead (e.g., transport – Highway Transportation System - Highway Bridge).

The TURNkey FWCR platform does not provide estimates for the damage to non-structural elements, fixtures or fittings. If these are needed then the end-user may be able to link the damage states (and the mean damage ratio) provided by the TURNkey FWCR platform to an assessment of the performance of non-structural elements, fixtures and fittings in their buildings through discussions with their technical consultants and/or suppliers. Similarly, human and economic loss estimates require data input by end-users. Users need to provide the platform with information on the number of people expected to be inside a building, the monetary value of the structural and non-structural elements of the building, and the value of equipment fixtures and fittings, different loss ratios etc. The estimates are then calculated on the basis of this data and generic or bespoke fragility and loss functions. The TURNkey FWCR platform can also combine structural damage and loss estimates to provide an assessment of the functionality level (e.g. 20%, 30% functionality) of the building for each earthquake scenario being evaluated. Again, the software team emphasised that this functionality loss would only

be based on estimation of the structural damage and would be at the building and built asset portfolio level, and not functional unit level within the building.

9.3.1.2 *Early activation of disaster management plans to improve employee and patient safety*

The fact that the TURNkey FWCR platform will not issue RAG alerts before a (first) major earthquake event, reduces the effectiveness of any early activation of the hospitals disaster management and response plans aimed at ensuring safety and checking that response systems are fully functioning in the time (72 hours' notice) immediately preceding an earthquake. However, the ability of the TURNkey FWCR platform to provide periodic updates (in the form of probability gain), which could be daily, weekly, monthly or at any other time period specified by the end-user organisation could allow medium-term (2 weeks' notice) instances to be activated (although this would be dependent on the change being considered significant enough by the hospital risk manager to initiate pre-earthquake disaster protocols). This said, the decision to initiate such protocols (e.g., preparing and testing emergency facilities, checking logistics and supply levels etc.) would be the responsibility of the end-user organisation and TURNkey would not take any responsibility if these were initiated in response to false-positive or false-negative alarms. The suitability of using probability gain will be investigated further in the PAR Cycle 3 when final simulation functionality is incorporated in the TURNkey platform.

9.3.1.3 *Minimise business disruption*

The simulation facility provided by the TURNkey FWCR platform would allow the development, review and testing of the hospital's disaster management plans against a range of different earthquake scenarios that reflect the hospital's local context and circumstances. It could provide information on physical vulnerabilities (e.g., vulnerability levels, damage grades, economic losses, amounts of debris, the functionality for EF and CIS) and social vulnerabilities (e.g., casualties, number of homeless people, number of shelters), using the default data/library or user-defined input data. The simulations would provide the hospital's managers with an estimate of the structural damage states of their built assets according to the EMS(98) damage grades, either by using typical building typologies or by providing bespoke fragility curves. TURNkey would also provide information to support risk management with structural damage and loss estimates, which, again, could be based on default loss ratios contained within the scientific engine or bespoke loss ratios provided by the hospital. To be clear, the platform is not designed to manage risk on behalf of the end-user. Instead, it is designed to provide information that could help decision-makers take actions. As outlined, the platform also provides a DSS system that could support this. The DSS results would be calculated on the basis of a multi-criteria decision-making methodology using cost-benefit analysis. They would categorise user-defined actions (and inaction) into cost-benefit classes and indicate what (in)actions would optimize value. At the time of the workshop the DSS was only partially integrated into the scientific engine. *NB: the DSS integration will not be ready by January 2022 to be shown during PAR Cycle 3.*

Whilst the TURNkey FWCR platform will not provide damage assessments or loss ratios for non-structural building elements, fixtures or fittings, the primary data (shake maps, PGA, structural damage states, etc.) from the TURNkey FWCR platform could be used by the hospitals consultants/suppliers as input data into bespoke risk assessment procedures for their system's functional performance response to the earthquake simulation scenario, which in turn could inform the hospital's overall risk assessment of its likely functional performance levels following the simulated earthquake.

The ability to use bespoke data (rather than generic data) to generate the simulations should increase the level of confidence in the outputs from the scenarios. The ability to rerun simulations for different building fragility curves should support the evaluation of different building related mitigation strategies linked to major structural interventions. This would significantly enhance the development

of medium to long term disaster management plans. The integration between simulations and business continuity and disaster management plans will be explored further in Task 7.3.

9.3.1.4 Joint planning

It became clear throughout the discussions that the simulation functionalities of the TURNkey FWCR platform are designed primarily as informational tools to inform end-user led planning and risk management, and not primarily as operational tools. It also became clear that, whilst the TURNkey FWCR platform could be applied to individual built assets (particularly high priority built assets) it would need to use bespoke fragility curves and loss ratio factors generated for each asset, which would probably incur considerable cost to the end-user.

A potentially useful future application of the TURNkey FWCR platform would be at the system level where the probabilities underlying damage states would support strategic planning decisions about the long-term location (or relocation) of critical high priority assets. However, the algorithm for path recommendation for emergency response and the associated Bayesian risk assessment for a network system developed in D4.8 (Gehl, et al., 2021) have not yet been integrated into the scientific engine due to the lack of generalizability. As such, *TURNkey can currently provide the functionality level of highway bridges as individual infrastructures, but not as a network infrastructure system.* If this were made possible in some future iteration, it would allow vertical integration between, for example, potential damage to a transportation network and potential damage to high priority assets. Such vertical integration would allow a more holistic assessment of potential interacting vulnerabilities. This is important because, whilst the high priority building may be functional, it may not be easily accessible to users. These issues will be investigated further during the development of the business cases in Task 7.3.

9.3.1.5 Simulation use cases - final comments

Throughout the discussions it became clear that the primary role of the TURNkey FWCR platform before a major earthquake event occurs is as a risk management, preparation and planning tool, rather than a disaster management tool. The potential benefits to risk planning offered by the ability to consider the performance of built assets (as either the building or system level) and potential losses resulting from a range of scenarios would provide a much richer dataset from which to develop risk management and response plans and evaluate the potential of physical mitigation interventions, and support training exercises, to reduce the impact that an earthquake would have on the hypothetical hospital's performance. As such, it was concluded that, whilst all the hypothetical use cases were applicable to a greater or lesser degree, the longer term and strategic use cases, rather than the short-term operational use cases, were likely to be of greatest benefit in allowing the hospital to better manage its earthquake risks.

9.3.2 The application of the TURNkey during an earthquake event

Before discussing EEW and RRE in detail, a discussion was held as to how the hypothetical hospital would access the TURNkey FWCR platform in real-time. At the beginning of the TURNkey project, no decision was made as to whether critical infrastructure and business organisations would have direct access to the TURNkey FWCR platform, or whether access would be through a national agency, such as civil protection. However, from discussions with civil protection (and emergency responders) and the software team, it is now clear that access will be through civil protection, who will, at their discretion, grant direct access to the TURNkey FWCR platform to key stakeholders and personnel. Whilst this does not change the data/information that the TURNkey FWCR platform can provide, it

could introduce a time delay (potentially of significance for EEW) or limit the range of individuals who will receive the information (potentially of significance to RRE). Whilst the relationship between the primary TURNkey FWCR platform (assumed to be civil protection) and the ultimate end-user has not yet been explored in detail (it will be addressed in task 7.3) the assumption used for the workshop was that a relationship is in place in which the civil protection will authorise direct access to the TURNkey FWCR platform for the hypothetical hospital's key disaster risk management employees.

Based on this assumption the software team explained the types of information that the TURNkey FWCR platform will provide during an earthquake:

- alerts (magnitude, location)
- EMS-98 intensity map
- and shakemap

NB: EEW does not provide a lead time or damage and loss estimates (the latter are provided as part of RRE)

Two types of early warning alert are issued, the first is based on regional earthquake sensors and is managed through the country's national seismic survey; the second through on-site TURNkey sensors, which detect the P wave and give a warning that the more intensive S wave is imminent.

9.3.2.1 Warning alert and early estimate of ground shaking

Once an earthquake has occurred, the TURNkey FWCR platform will generate an alert if the predicted level of ground shaking (PGA) at a specific building location exceeds a predefined threshold level. The predicted level of ground shaking for a built asset will depend upon the geophysical characteristics of the earthquake (i.e., the type of fault, epicentre and magnitude) and the distance of the built asset from the epicentre as well as the geology of the area between the epicentre and the built asset. The threshold level will be set by the end-user. When the threshold level is exceeded, the TURNkey FWCR platform issues an alert as well as an estimate of the intensity of the expected ground shaking. The TURNkey FWCR platform will communicate the national seismic institutes' alert to the end-user. The alert would most probably be received in the organisations' control room, which would need to be continuously monitored. The TURNkey FWCR platform could theoretically be directly linked to an organisation's legacy (critical) systems, however facilitating this is not in scope of the TURNkey project. In its current setup this functionality would have to be activated by the platform user (e.g. stopping vertical transport systems at the nearest safe location, activating backup protocols, switching critical equipment to a 'safe mode' etc.). This includes alert to an organisation's general public address system, warning occupants of the potential for imminent ground shaking and advising them to take precautionary measures (e.g. drop, cover, hold on).

EEW works for both the mainshock and for aftershocks. The shakemap generated by EEW has only one purpose: whether or not to generate an alert. OEF will update the long-term and short-term probability of exceeding certain shaking level defined by the user and the probability gain. RRE will update the shakemap and damage estimates based on the real-time observations. Thus, once a major shock has occurred, the TURNkey FWCR platform will start issuing aftershock warnings for additional shocks as part of its EEW dashboard. Using RRE, the platform will also regularly update the shake maps and damage and loss estimates, as more detailed information becomes available from the sensor networks. This is discussed further below under '9.3.7. RRE'.

9.3.2.2 *Impact of EEW on the hospital's hypothetical use cases*

Two general findings can be drawn from the discussions on the role and potential benefits of the TURNkey FWCR platform earthquake early warning function to a critical infrastructure or business organisation.

9.3.2.2.1 *Personal safety*

The TURNkey FWCR platform will issue a warning alert if the predicted level of ground shaking at the hospital's specified locations exceed a pre-set threshold. On receipt of this alert, the hospital's control room can instigate its predefined disaster management protocols and standard operating procedures. The expected lead time between receiving an alert and strong ground shaking arriving could vary from zero seconds to a few tens of seconds. The precise lead time will depend upon the earthquake's epicentre and local geological conditions. Given that protecting the safety of building occupants is the key concern of the earthquake early warning use cases, it is likely that on receipt of an alert the control room will initiate a general audible alarm across the building in either the form of a clearly recognisable sound or a short automated message. Whilst it would be possible to link the issuing of the alarm automatically with the TURNkey FWCR platform alert, this would involve connecting the TURNkey FWCR platform to legacy systems, which is not currently within the scope of the TURNkey project. As such, the alarm would have to be triggered manually. The specific action that building occupants would take on receiving an audible alert would depend upon their role and the tasks they were doing at the time. For general occupants of the building the protocols would advise them to mentally prepare for ground shaking, and if possible, to evacuate the building or to drop-cover-hold. For medical staff the alert could mean to adopt specific protocols, such as stop medical procedures or initiate evacuation. Although not explored with the current end-user stakeholders, as the TURNkey FWCR platform alert will not be automatically linked to the organisation's alarm system, it might be possible for organisations to have more than one alarm setting (e.g. different alarms which generate different actions depending upon expected lead time to ground shaking.). This possibility will be explored in more detail in Task 7.3.

9.3.2.2.2 *Protecting and monitoring critical systems*

In addition to ensuring the personal safety of building occupants, on receiving an earthquake early warning alert, control room staff could initiate a controlled shutdown of critical building systems to a 'safe' operating position. For example, vertical transportation systems could be rerouted to stop at a safe location; automatic doors could be opened allowing egress from the building (security issues would have to be taken into consideration), and equipment that is vulnerable to shaking could be set to a 'safe' or 'park' mode. Although the TURNkey FWCR platform could theoretically be directly linked to an organisation's legacy (critical) systems, this functionality will not be developed during the TURNkey project. As such, the TURNkey FWCR platform assumes manual intervention will be required to activate earthquake response protocols.

9.3.2.2.3 *EEW use cases - final comments*

It is clear that all the hospital's hypothetical EEW use cases could potentially be supported by the TURNkey FWCR platform. The integration of TURNkey with the hypothetical hospital's IT legacy systems would further support this, but this is beyond the scope of the current TURNkey project.

9.3.3 **The application of TURNkey after an earthquake event**

9.3.3.1 *Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)*

After a major earthquake has occurred, the TURNkey FWCR platform continuously monitors the heightened seismicity and generates probabilistic 'forecasts' of additional ground shaking (e.g.,

aftershocks). These 'forecasts' enable the operative managers of an organization to plan actions to mitigate the impact of aftershocks and minimize damage. This is part of TURNkey's OEF functionality, included in the OEF dashboard of the TURNkey FWCR platform. After an earthquake event, OEF updates the long-term and short-term probability of exceeding a certain shaking level defined by the user – as well as the probability gain.

TURNkey will not develop a Red-Amber-Green functionality for OEF by the end of the project. However, end-users could in the future potentially define Red-Amber-Green (RAG) alerts based on their tolerance of the changes in the hazard threat. They could tailor this to the building typology, occupancy class and functionality of their assets. If they did defined RAG alerts in advance (e.g., if the short-term probability of certain shaking level defined by the user is 10% higher than that of the background seismicity: amber alert), the RAG alerts could be presented on the rapid response (RRE) dashboard. To deliver this, certain configurations and GUI would need to be set up beforehand. TURNkey will not issue OEF alerts (e.g., through the mobile app to provide people working in the field with probabilistic information about additional ground shaking). Instead, it will issue EEW alerts.

9.3.3.2 Early estimates of damage and losses

After a major earthquake event, the TURNkey FWCR platform dashboard will continuously update its shakemaps as well as its damage and loss estimates. A short time (approximately 5 minutes) after an alert has been issued, the TURNkey FWCR platform will generate estimates for an initial shakemap. On the basis of this initial shakemap, it will calculate initial damage states and loss assessments. It is not possible for the TURNkey FWCR platform to issue an all-clear alert. However, the TURNkey FWCR platform will start issuing aftershock warnings for additional shocks as part of its EEW dashboard. Using RRE, the platform will also regularly update the shake maps and damage and loss estimates, as more detailed information becomes available from the sensor networks. RRE will update the shakemap and damage estimates based on real-time data generated from the TURNkey sensors and authorised eye-witness reporting. As outlined, the TURNkey FWCR platform will not issue ground shaking alerts (e.g., RAG) but it will generate shakemaps and then indicate damage using different colours, which express different damage grades. It will do so throughout the response and recovery period.

There was a general discussion about the reliability of the information, damage states and loss estimates. The software team explained the science and technical details behind them. They explained that unlike with OEF, in RRE the actual PGA is observed. *In RRE, the term probability (e.g., of exceedance) has no place. It is only used in OEF for aftershocks or in probabilistic simulations.* Similarly, RRE does not rely on simulations. Once an earthquake event has happened, all generated results are no longer probabilistic. The updated RRE shakemap provides reliable hazard information. The initial estimation of damage and loss are based on the assigned fragility functions and models. However, after experiencing earthquakes, the structural response may deviate from the selected functions/models. Thus, without field investigation of the actual damage, the damage and loss estimation can only be used as a reference. The uncertainty of the updated shakemap based on the real-time observation is expected to be lower than the initial shakemap generated in the EEW process.

Another point that was discussed was the location of TURNkey sensors. TURNkey sensors could be located in the basement of the buildings to record the ground acceleration at the base of the building. Once an earthquake has occurred, these sensors would provide real-time recordings of ground acceleration that would then be used to generate real-time damage and loss estimates. D4.8 provides an example for on-site RRE. *There is no communication between the TURNkey engine and the on-site data: this is not in scope of the TURNkey project.* If the building sensor is part of the GEMPA network, the engine could in the future use this information.

9.3.3.3 Access to the TURNkey app

The TURNkey app is a phone-based app that will allow users to receive alerts and upload data to the TURNkey FWCR platform. The app will issue EEW alerts about potential forthcoming ground shaking. The TURNkey FWCR scientific engine will calculate the estimated ground motion based on its interpretation of an actual event. If ground shaking occurs, the mobile app will issue an 'ARE YOU SAFE' request and the user will need to respond 'I'M SAFE'. If a user does not respond with 'IM SAFE' then the TURNkey FWCR platform will send a message to the user's manager to say a response has not been received and to suggest further investigation. If ground-shaking occurs again after an initial major earthquake event, then the TURNkey FWCR platform will issue an audible early warning alert to anybody who has access to the mobile app. As outlined, TURNkey does not provide the lead time till impact.

9.3.3.4 Impact of RRE on the hospital's hypothetical rapid response use cases

Two general findings can be drawn from the discussions on the role and potential benefits of the TURNkey FWCR platform RRE functions.

9.3.3.5 Rapid estimate of ground shaking, building damage and losses

Following the general discussions, a detailed discussion was then held to identify the specific data/information the hypothetical hospital would have access to when responding to an earthquake. The assumption would be that the hospital had already developed an earthquake response plan using TURNkey simulation. The assumption would be that once damage had occurred, these plans would be activated, and the hospital had convened its first-line emergency response committee. The first RRE information the hospital would receive from the TURNkey FWCR platform would be a very early (within minutes) assessment of ground shaking and structural damage. After that, the platform would constantly update the shakemap based on the actual ground shaking observed at the stations or reported by the citizen, which would lead to a more accurate shakemap for the hospital's buildings and site. It would also provide better estimates of the damage profiles and loss estimates for these assets – provided building details (either generic or bespoke) had previously been provided to the TURNkey FWCR platform. In addition to ground shaking warnings, the TURNkey FWCR platform would run regularly (e.g. every 2 hours) a new assessment of the hazard threat level as part of TURNkey's post event OEF functionality. The frequency of new assessments would reduce over time as the likelihood of shocks decreases. Note, in all cases TURNkey would not issue an 'it is safe' message, it would always focus on a negative message 'it is not safe'.

9.3.3.6 Monitoring and coordination of recovery actions

TURNkey transmits RRE information to the hospital's key employees about the likelihood of potential ground shaking after a major earthquake event and the estimated severity of the earthquake, including

estimated damages and losses. This information is regularly updated based on field observation through the TURNkey App. This is because, in addition to *transmitting* information, the TURNkey FWCR platform will also *receive* near real-time information about the actual state of buildings and assets in terms of their damage level and functional performance from the hospital's key employees 'eyewitness sources' on the ground. Suitably trained and authorised employees will be able to upload damage assessments against the EMS98 damage grades, including free field text describing the damage and photo images of damaged buildings. They can also provide estimates of the functional capacity of the building against predefined functional performance levels provided to the TURNkey FWCR platform by the hospital during the commissioning of the software. Once the eyewitness reports have been validated the information is entered into the scientific engine which will use the data to update damage and loss estimates and present this information in graphical form (e.g., a shakemap or region map with damage state of critical buildings shown at their geographical location) on the dashboard. The TURNkey FWCR platform has the ability to store contact details of key hospital personnel (which could include family members) along with pre-composed email messages that can be sent to contact lists as and when required. In addition, precomposed social media messages can also be stored along with social media feeds, again these can be issued as and when required.

The TURNkey FWCR platform has the ability to store the hospital's standard disaster management response protocols as part of its dashboard. These protocols, combined with the contact details described above, can be used to initiate standard response actions, which along with the real-time feedback facility provided through the TURNkey app will be able to confirm whether the action has been started, partially completed or fully completed. For each action, the TURNkey FWCR platform will allow the hospital's managers to drill down through the list of actions.

9.3.3.7 REE use cases - final comments

In essence, after an earthquake event, the TURNkey FWCR platform is a decision support tool that provides the latest information from the sensors and from eyewitness reporting of experts. It facilitates the activation of the hospital's pre-programmed actions, following a review by disaster management committees. It also helps coordinate critical staff assessing the real-time impact of the earthquake on built assets and functional performance in the field. The ability of the TURNkey FWCR platform to integrate 'eyewitness' observations of actual damage states and functionality levels into the scientific engine means that the hospital's standard response protocols can be customised to reflect the actual damage state of the most critical buildings and systems, and response and maintenance teams can be programmed to work to restore the hospital's functionality in the most effective way. This would include the ability to monitor progress of repair and provide regular updates on the likely timescale to returning different levels of functional performance (e.g. 30%, 50%, 70% functionality etc.). As the hospital begins to return to higher levels of functionality, the use of the TURNkey FWCR platform dashboard and mobile app will provide the hospital's employees, patients and managers with increased confidence that staff and patients have a level of advanced warning of potential ground shaking through the EEW alarm system and app.

In addition to supporting actual repair work within the hospital, the real-time updating of damage states and functional performance provided by 'eyewitness' reporting will allow logistics managers to initiate supply chains in a priority order to ensure that the most critical items needed to support the return of the hospital's functionality are identified, located and procured first (e.g. alternative power and fuel supplies, replacements for damaged equipment etc.). If the TURNkey FWCR platform is also being operated at the health sector level, health managers from different facilities would have access to functionality levels of different health units across the sector, enabling better patient management through relocation of patients to those units that are best placed to help them.

9.4 Summary and general discussion

The hypothetical hospital scenario provided a ‘role-play’ scenario to test the degree to which the TURNkey FWCR platform could deliver benefits in disaster risk management to a typical critical infrastructure business organisation. A team of academic researchers developed a series of hypothetical use cases, derived from the specific use cases developed in the first and 2nd PAR cycles, and presented these through detailed discussions with the TURNkey software development team. They did so to identify the data inputs needed from a critical infrastructure or business organisation to operationalise the TURNkey FWCR platform and explore how the outputs from the TURNkey FWCR platform could inform disaster risk management. The hypothetical hospital scenario focused on the questions:

1. *Why should the hypothetical hospital invest time and effort in using the TURNkey FWCR platform?*
2. *Could the TURNkey FWCR platform help the hospital better manage its earthquake disaster risk, and if so, how?*

The TURNkey FWCR platform development team described in detail how the platform could be used before, during and after an earthquake event to identify potential impacts on a range of earthquake simulation scenarios (before an earthquake) and impacts of an actual earthquake (after an earthquake) based upon real-time recordings of ground shaking and building damage states. The TURNkey FWCR platform can also provide an earthquake early warning alert (once an earthquake has occurred but before ground shaking reaches the asset) that can enable employees and patients who are in the hospital to prepare for ground shaking and take safety precautions (e.g. drop-cover-hold.). To this extent, at this stage in its development the TURNkey FWCR platform has demonstrated its potential to contribute to effective disaster management planning; help protect and reduce human and financial losses; and support the response and recovery of a hospital following an earthquake. Although the hypothetical scenario could not directly quantify the time and effort that would be required to develop and implement the TURNkey FWCR platform in a typical hospital, it did identify the process steps that would be required for such an implementation and these, along with wider business implementation issues (e.g. governance, IT security etc.) will be used as the basis of developing business models in Task 7.3.

To help understand how the TURNkey FWCR platform could be used to help the hospital better manage its earthquake disaster risk, a series of hypothetical hospital use cases were developed prior the workshop from the revised use cases develop during the 2nd PAR cycle. Eight use cases, describing 81 potential applications were identified (note some potential applications were duplicated between the use cases) where the TURNkey FWCR platform could potentially have a direct effect on the hospital’s disaster risk management. In essence, before an earthquake happens the TURNkey FWCR platform should be considered primarily as a strategic planning tool rather than an operational management tool. The ability of the TURNkey FWCR platform to model a wide range of potential earthquake scenarios against specific attributes of the hospital’s built assets should provide customised damage and loss estimates which, when combined with changes to the estimates predicted as a result of structural mitigation actions, should support the wider business case for specific physical interventions. This, combined with the ability of the simulations to support disaster planning should collectively reduce the hospital’s risks to an earthquake. Problems encountered by the TURNkey scientific and software teams to provide RAG alerts for OEF (this activity was a feasibility study in the TURNkey project and not something that was guaranteed) into the TURNkey FWCR platform does reduce the effectiveness of some of the operational application areas; in particular the ability to realistically initiate the hospital’s disaster management plans in anticipation of an imminent

earthquake in all but very specific geographical locations. This limitation will be explored in more detail during the development of the final set of use cases and business models in Task 7.3.

At the middle stage of the earthquake sequence (i.e., during the earthquake) the TURNkey FWCR platform demonstrated its ability to deliver against all of the hypothetical use cases. The TURNkey FWCR platform can deliver an alert to a national/regional control centre that will then issue an alert to the hospital. Access to TURNkey information depends on the preferences of the relevant local authority: they can in the GUI settings specify if alerts should go directly to operators of critical infrastructures. The relationship between local authorities and other end-users of the TURNkey platform will be explored in more detail during the development of the final set of use cases and business models in Task 7.3. Whilst the TURNkey FWCR platform early warning alert could be directly linked to the hospitals critical systems, facilitating automatic shutdown or failsafe mode, this is outside of the current TURNkey project and would be something that would be explored on an ad-hoc basis should an individual hospital client request it.

In the final stage of the earthquake sequence (i.e., after the earthquake) the TURNkey FWCR platform again demonstrated its ability to deliver against all of the hypothetical use cases. The TURNkey FWCR platform will monitor in near real-time the actual damage and loss situation of the hospital's built assets through 'eye witness' reports by the hospital's response teams on the ground. This will support the rapid deployment of a hospital's (and its subcontractors) recovery and repair teams to the most critically damaged assets from a functionality perspective. The mobile app will ensure that those recovery and repair teams working on site can receive EEW earthquake alerts. Furthermore, the 'I'm safe' function of the app will allow hospital managers in the control room to monitor the status of the repair and recovery teams if a further earthquake shock were to occur. The ability to monitor the status of recovery and repair activities will also enable targeted actions along the hospitals supply chain to secure critical resources needed for the recovery and to keep other stakeholders informed of the functionality level of the hospital during the earthquake recovery.

10 General Assembly 19/11/21

The final action of the PAR Cycle 2 was to reflect on the results from the cycle and set the agenda for PAR Cycle 3. This reflection started at the TURNkey General Assembly attended by the majority of TURNkey partners (see D8.13) and continued by email correspondence after the event.

At the General Assembly on the 19th of November, the TURNkey consortium came together online. The meeting started with an overview of the results of PAR Cycle2. The final use cases were presented online to the participants. This session started with an overview of the use cases of civil protection and first responders which was presented by NTC. After that, the use cases for business organisations and critical infrastructure providers were shown to participants. At the end of each use case participants were asked to give their feedback and input. Some made comments during the online meeting and others provided feedback via email.

The following general points were raised in response to the presentation of the use cases:

1. EEW is not compatible with humans checking the data due to the delays this causes. Human checking requires that 24/7 there is someone ready to validate EEW data in less than a second. It also requires this person to have access to other data in order to cross-reference and validate the EEW data. It's not clear what this data would be or where it would come from. In Mexico, civil protection is involved in the dissemination of EEW information. They dismantled their EEW input for these very reasons.

2. OEF and scenario-based simulations are not the same. OEF provides a probabilistic estimate of how, in a given area, the short-term seismic hazard changes compared to the long term hazard. That is, it provides seismic hazards, particularly in the form of daily probability of exceedance and/or daily probability gain. OEF does not entail running potential scenarios for future events. It does not estimate the epicentre either. As such, it is not possible to develop a scenario from information such as "there is an increased probability of a M5 in the area over the next 5 days".
3. OEF information about seismic hazards can be combined with other information to create vulnerability/loss models, however, such models are separate from OEF. Likewise, shakemaps are not part of OEF.
4. One participant noted that the variation in the time-dependent hazard on which OEF is based is meaningful, particularly in the duration of seismic heightening after a mainshock. As such, OEF DSS systems can use these variations to inform particular (short-medium term) mitigation actions. Other participants expressed the view that the variation was negligible and that OEF therefore cannot meaningfully inform operational decision making.
5. Regarding Red Amber Green (RAG) alerts for OEF, one participant suggested that this need not be eliminated. In task 3.5 a set of probability gain ranges (1, 10, 100, 1000) was agreed to express the level of seismic heightening before a mainshock and also during an aftershock sequence. The same could potentially be used for RAG alerts.
6. Regarding where TURNkey should sit, there are two options: one option is that a public authority buys the platform and gives access to external stakeholders like critical infrastructure providers. The other option is that critical infrastructure providers buy it on their own. In case of the former, TURNkey information may need to be manually evaluated.

Regarding specific use cases, the following points were raised:

- UC5 'TURNkey to reduce damage to critical systems allowing faster recovery after an earthquake'. One participant highlighted that – for reasons of governance and legal responsibility - it is important to clarify who the intended end-user is. They pointed out that in the context of a critical infrastructure provider this UC is straightforward as they directly control the relevant assets. However, it is different when the end-user is external (like civil protection) because they have only indirect control over the relevant assets. In the case of the latter, lines of responsibility need to be clarified: i.e., who is responsible for shutting down assets or systems when TURNkey issues an EEW alert.
- UC5 'TURNkey to reduce damage to critical systems allowing faster recovery after an earthquake'. One participant highlighted that facilitating automated EEW actions is important to TURNkey's sales model. They pointed out that TURNkey currently only facilitates the manual initiation of shut-down actions or go to park modes. They flagged that whilst it is possible to change this to automatic in the future, it is not feasible to do so within the project timeline.
- UC7 'TURNkey to initiate rapid activation of disaster management plans during and after an earthquake' I think that the app has been defined for users that are in a large geographical area. In the case of a critical infrastructure provider, it may be useful for an electric or gas network manager. For infrastructure like hospitals (or a single electric power plant) it probably is not the proper instrument. If you stay in a hospital why use a safety check? Maybe if the hospital is

collapsing, but in this case, you're already in trouble. So I don't think UC7 is really applicable for [individual] critical infrastructure [assets].

After all the use cases were presented, the status of the TURNkey platform was discussed. An overview was given of its development and integration. Next, plans for the testing and validation of the platform were discussed including ideas for ARU and NTC to conduct demonstrations in the field with stakeholders. The option of doing a workshop with test bed leaders was also discussed, with data streaming from the testbeds after the end of the project.

Finally, the consortium discussed plans for a final demo in Alicante. Based on the input and feedback given during the General Assembly and also in emails that were received afterwards, the use cases that were presented at the General Assembly were revised. The final version can be found in section 14.

11 The FWCR Platform: What Turnkey Provides When

On the second day of the workshop at NORSAR, after the hospital scenario had been completed, participants systematically went through the end-user requirements and discussed whether these features were possible from a scientific or engineering point of view and whether they fell within the scope of the TURNkey project. Additional detail on what the TURNkey FWCR platform will – and will not - deliver was provided by NORSAR in writing, in the format of feedback and comments on an earlier draft of Section 9. These findings have been included in 'Appendix G: Table of Features' and also in 'Appendix H: Revised Use Cases'. Below follows a summary of the feedback that was provided. It is structured following the earthquake hazard timeline: before an earthquake event; during an earthquake event; and after an earthquake event.

11.1 Before an Earthquake Event: Simulations

Before an earthquake event, TURNkey provides the possibility to run *simulations*. It does not provide OEF – see section 11.3 on OEF.

- **Simulations are initiated by the end-user:** TURNkey runs simulations when end-users (e.g., a local/regional authority) request them via the GUI for the purpose of short-term/long-term risk reduction planning. Simulations do not generate or issue any alerts (e.g., RAG).
- **Types of Simulation:** simulations can be carried out before any earthquake event. The main purpose of these simulations is to facilitate short-term or long-term risk reduction planning.

TURNkey provides 2 types:

1. Probabilistic simulations based on background seismicity;
 2. Deterministic simulations, based on pre-defined inputs (e.g., magnitude, location, depth);
- **The information provided by simulations:**
 1. Probabilistic simulations provide maps showing the periodic (daily) probability gain. They do *not* provide shake maps. Probabilistic simulations compute the resulting physical impacts (damage) and socio-economic impacts. Finally, they provide DSS based on a cost/benefit analysis of different actions.
 2. Deterministic simulations provide shake maps (i.e., ground shaking maps). They compute the resulting physical impacts (damage) and socio-economic impacts. Finally, they provide DSS based on a cost/benefit analysis of different actions.

- **Access and control over the information generated through the simulations:** The owner of the TURNkey platform (e.g., a local authority) determines who receives the information and at what level of detail. They can enter their decision(s) into TURNkey GUI.

As outlined, simulations do not generate information about real-time events. As such, in all probability, the owner of the TURNkey platform (say, a local authority) will manually send the information to relevant stakeholders, after they have finished analysing the results of the simulations. These stakeholders (e.g., operators of essential facilities like hospitals or operators of critical infrastructures like tunnels) can then use this information to take actions that can help reduce their vulnerability and risk. The local authority would be able to customise the information to suit the recipient, e.g., an operator of a hospital would only receive information about the hospital facilities/buildings whereas an operator of the tunnel would only receive information about the tunnel.

11.2 During an Earthquake Event: EEW

- **EEW is activated automatically:** TURNkey's EEW is activated automatically as a result of sensor data
- **The information provided by EEW:**
 - Magnitude, location
 - The first estimate of intensity (in terms of EMS-98 scales) and a shake map (ground shaking)
 - An alert if the predicted ground shaking (PGA) exceeds pre-defined threshold levels
 - The platform's EEW functionality *does not* provide the lead time
 - The platform's EEW functionality *does not* compute damages and losses
- **Access and control over EEW information:** The owner of the TURNkey platform (e.g., a local/regional authority) determines who receives the EEW information, in which mode (automatically or manually) and at what level of detail. They can enter their decision(s) into TURNkey GUI.
- *NB. The TURNkey platform doesn't take any actions, it only provides EEW information*

When relevant stakeholders (e.g., operators of essential facilities like hospitals or operators of critical infrastructures like tunnels) receive the EEW information they initiate actions following their existing safety and security protocols, e.g., shutdown facilities. Whether they receive EEW information for a given earthquake event depends on the thresholds set for their facilities and infrastructures (which have been pre-defined).

The local/regional authority can also enter into the TURNkey GUI whether information should be sent to the general public or media, and at what level of detail. This will most probably be done manually and not automatically.

11.3 After an earthquake Event: OEF

- **What the OEF feature provides:** TURNkey does not provide OEF *before* an earthquake event. It only provides OEF after an earthquake has occurred, for additional shocks. As such, 'OEF' in the context of TURNkey generally means 'OEF for aftershocks'. However, it was decided not to call the feature 'OEF for aftershocks' because after a mainshock event it is not always the case that all events that come after are aftershocks. It is possible that one of them is another mainshock. As such, in TURNkey this feature is simply called OEF and not OEF for aftershocks.

- **OEF is activated automatically:** TURNkey's OEF is activated automatically after EEW.
- **The information provided by OEF:**
 - The platform's OEF functionality generates maps showing changes in hazards and probability gain
 - The platform's OEF DSS functionality can be activated manually. It is based on a cost-benefit analysis for different actions. Whether it makes sense to do so depends on the impact of the first earthquake event:
 - If the first earthquake event (mainshock) caused severe damage, there is no point in computing damage and socio-economic losses for the OEF DSS. However, if the first event (mainshock) caused no or minor damage, it makes sense to compute damage and socio-economic losses and run the OEF DSS.
- **Information *not* provided by OEF:**
 - The platform's OEF functionality does not compute physical impacts (damage) or socio-economic impacts
 - The platform's OEF functionality does not generate shake maps
 - The platform's OEF functionality does not generate or send alerts (e.g., RAG).
- **Access and control over OEF information:** The owner of the TURNkey platform (e.g., a local/regional authority) determines who receives the OEF information and at what level of detail. They can enter their decision(s) into TURNkey GUI.
 - These stakeholders (e.g., operators of essential facilities like hospitals or operators of critical infrastructures like tunnels) can then use this information to take actions that can help reduce their vulnerability and risk. The local authority would be able to customise the information to suit the recipient, e.g., an operator of a hospital would only receive information about the hospital facilities/buildings whereas an operator of the tunnel would only receive information about the tunnel.

11.4 After an earthquake event: RRE

- **RRE is activated automatically:** TURNkey's OEF is activated automatically after EEW and if the pre-defined thresholds are exceeded
- **The information provided by RRE:**
 - Shakemap (ground shaking) and intensity
 - For general buildings/built area: damage and fatalities, the number of homeless people, required number of shelters, safe zones. The information is regularly updated based on feedback from infield responders via the TURNkey app.
 - For essential facilities (e.g., hospitals, schools): damage and level of functionality. The information is regularly updated based on feedback from infield responders via the TURNkey app.
 - For critical infrastructure providers: damage and level of functionality. The information is regularly updated based on feedback from infield responders via the TURNkey app.
- **Information *not* provided by RRE:** the platform *does not* provide advice on what actions to take. These decisions will be up to the owner of the platform (e.g., local authority) based on the outcomes of the analysis. Some concrete examples: if the analysis shows that a given hospital

is not damaged, has enough capacity and is still 80-100% operational, then the local authority can instruct search and rescue teams to take injured people there. If the analysis shows that a school is not damaged, they can instruct that it be used as a safe zone and as a shelter for the homeless. Furthermore, knowing which highway bridges functional and which ones are not would inform in-field first responders' decisions as to which route to take for safety and emergency actions.

- **Access and control over RRE information:** the owner of the TURNkey platform (e.g., a local/regional authority) determines who receives the RRE information and at what level of detail. They can enter their decision(s) into TURNkey GUI.

In practice, relevant stakeholders will regularly be updated by the local/regional authorities. The RRE functionality makes it possible for this to be done automatically or manually.

In the TURNkey GUI authorities can also enter which information and at what level of detail to share with the general public. In practice, most of the information that will be shared will be safety instructions: e.g., 'take this route because the bridge is closed', or 'don't go to this zone because it is dangerous, instead go to safe zones where there are shelters and water', 'don't go to this hospital because is full / or only partially functional'.

NB. all these communications will be conducted through existing emergency communication channels.

11.5 Beta Version of the TURNkey Conceptual Model

Discussions during the workshop at NORSAR and the General Assembly Meeting in November informed a number of changes to the TURNkey concept model, which had been presented to the Consortium earlier that year in June. These changes have been depicted in Figure 11 below.

Key changes to the June 2021 TURNkey FWCR Concept Model

Figure 11 Key changes to the June 2021 TURNkey FWCR Concept Model

12 CONCLUSIONS AND 3RD ITERATION OF THE TURNKEY FWCR PLATFORM USE CASES

PAR Cycle 2 started in January 2021 with the translation of the 2nd TURNkey FWCR platform into a series of 5 virtual demonstrator video presentations that showed how the emerging FWCR platform could be used by end-user stakeholders (civil protection, emergency responders, critical infrastructure organisations and general business organisations) before, during and after an earthquake event to help these organisations better understand and manage their earthquake risks. The video demonstrators were developed in collaboration with the TURNkey scientific and software development teams against the 17 use cases developed in the PAR Cycle 1 and were used as the basis for testing the TURNkey FWCR platform against the use cases during the 2nd set of stakeholder interviews.

Stakeholder interviews were held with potential end-users in Iceland, France, the Netherlands, Greece, Romania and Italy in March and April 2021. They confirmed the general applicability of the use cases but highlighted the importance of TURNkey being customizable - and information/data access is carefully controlled. The functional requirements were explored by referring the end user's needs back to the software development team, the technical requirements were addressed by returning these to the science/engineering teams. The use cases were revised following the interviews, and the revised work was presented to the TURNkey consortium at the TURNkey annual meeting in June, where further feedback was received, and the use cases were accepted as the basis for the development of the 2nd set of operational models and tools.

At the same time as the use cases were tested, a SWOT analysis was undertaken, which started at the annual meeting in June and was concluded online via a survey with open text options. The SWOT analysis confirmed that the key opportunities and strengths of the TURNkey FWCR system were in line with those identified from the literature review of other systems done in PAR Cycle 1. It also identified the weaknesses and threats that needed to be addressed, such as the lack of a business model for TURNkey (weakness) and a potential failure to facilitate integration with existing national and organisational systems and processes (threat). The SWOT analysis also confirmed the general applicability of the use cases and informed their further development and fine-tuning. The revised use cases developed at the 2nd annual meeting were used as the basis of a two-day workshop held at NORSAR (19-20 of October) to test the operational tools and models that had been incorporated into the TURNkey FWCR platform. The civil protection and emergency responder use cases were tested using a checklist developed by NTC (and reported in detail in deliverable D2.10). As a result, the text 'rapidly populates' was removed from OEF. Furthermore, it was clarified in the RRE use cases that there are limitations to the extent to which information from different input sources can be centralised and integrated.

The critical infrastructure and business use cases were tested using a hypothetical hospital scenario modelled a typical earthquake sequence (before during and after an earthquake event.). As a result of the discussion a small number of changes were made to the use cases:

- Language - in particular, that describes the functionality and scope of the FWCR platform to non-technical (or semi-technical) individuals. It became clear during discussions that there was confusion about the precise meaning of some terminology, that would need to be removed during the final PAR cycle. For example, the inclusion of all TURNkey functionality prior to an earthquake into OEF caused confusion as some of the functionality of TURNkey in this area is not an aspect of OEF but general earthquake simulation.

- Access - a number of critical infrastructure providers wanted direct access to the TURNkey FWCR platform, whilst civil protection wanted all access to the platform to come through their organisation. This apparent conflict initially caused concern about possible delays to an earthquake early warning, and therefore its usefulness. In reality, providing civil protection grant the critical infrastructure organisation direct access to their version of the TURNkey FWCR platform this issue does not arise. Another issue with access was inputting data about the critical infrastructure assets, operating procedures, and personnel into the TURNkey FWCR platform. At present, there is no GUI for these activities; which limits the potential for critical infrastructure organisations to explore ‘what-if’ scenarios as part of their earthquake disaster management and business continuity planning.

The final workshop session consolidated the results from the previous sessions (i.e., the hospital scenario and the discussion of TURNkey’s features) against the use cases used in PAR Cycle 2 and made detailed amendments to each of these to reflect the end-user needs and technical feasibility of meeting these needs during the remainder of the project or post-project. These reflections then arrived at a final set of use cases that were presented to the full TURNkey consortium at the general assembly on 19 November 2021 where all participants were asked to reflect on the use cases and send written comments to ARU if they had any changes or suggestions for improvement. A number of comments and suggestions were made, and these were then incorporated into the use cases to be used in the 3rd PAR cycle (see section 14).

13 Next Steps

The discussions that concluded PAR Cycle 2 indicated that the vast majority of the TURNkey FWCR platform’s functionality has reached TRL 4 (technology demonstrated in the laboratory), with just a small part of the OEF system at TRL 3 (experimental proof of concept). The final stage in the TURNkey FWCR platform development is to test the system at TRL 5 (technology validated in a relevant environment). This activity forms the basis of the 3rd (and final) PAR cycle where the TURNkey FWCR platform will be demonstrated to critical infrastructure and business organisations in the testbeds, and their feedback used to inform the final TURNkey FWCR conceptual model. To support TRL 5 validation A final set of revised generic use cases are being developed and integrated into a holistic, end-to-end use case story, in which hypothetical critical infrastructure and business organisations, which will be located within a hypothetical city region subject to a major earthquake. This will be based on a simulated main shock-aftershock sequence similar to the M6.4 earthquake that occurred in Iceland on June 21, 2000. (The synthetic data will send from the sensor). A virtual demonstrator of the role of the TURNkey FWCR platform at each stage (OEF, EEW and RRE) of the earthquake sequence will be shown to critical infrastructure, business organisations, civil protection and emergency responders for their final thoughts and feedback. The validation activity will take place in February/March 2022 and will be reported as part of TURNkey Tasks 6.6, 7.3 and 7.4. As such, the next steps are:

- To develop an end-to-end use case story, based on the use cases discussed for both civil protection/emergency responders and critical infrastructure/business organisations, which would simulate the application of the TURNkey FWCR platform before, during and after an earthquake.
- The simulation would be based on a hypothetical city region and would include a small number of high priority buildings (e.g. a hospital, schools and a factory). The scenario will be similar to the M 6.4 Iceland event on June 21, 2000.

- The simulation would be built in advance and would be used during PAR Cycle 3 as a demonstrator to evaluate the final end-user response to the TURNkey FWCR platform, including civil protection, emergency responders, critical infrastructure and business organisations.
- The demonstrator would be used during the testbed workshop to be organised at NORSAR in February/March 2022.
- And, finally, the demonstrator would also inform the development of a real-world application of the TURNkey FWCR platform to the Alicante simulation.

14 Revised Use Cases

This section presents a summary of the revised use cases that will form the basis of PAR Cycle 3. A more detailed version is provided in Appendix H.

14.1 Civil Protection and First Responders

14.1.1 Use Case 1: Supporting damage prevention

14.1.2 Use Case 2: Enabling a more timely and accurate response

14.1.3 Use Case 3: Supporting prioritisation, resource allocation and coordination

14.2 General Business and Critical Infrastructure Providers

14.2.1 Use Case 1: Disaster and risk management planning at the individual site/building level or organisation/sector level before an earthquake event

Current status: Possible by the end of the project. TURNkey doesn't have a GUI to allow direct input of bespoke data

Next steps: Develop a GUI for bespoke data entry. This **will not** be developed during the current project.

14.2.2 Use Case 2: Support the business case for mitigation action to reduce the impact on critical service/business function

Current status: Possible by the end of the project. TURNkey doesn't have a GUI to allow direct input of bespoke data.

Next steps: Develop a GUI for bespoke data entry. This **will not** be developed during the current project.

14.2.3 Use Case 3: Support early activation of disaster management and business continuity plans

Current status: Possible by the end of the project.

Next steps: Evaluate the feasibility of developing a RAG like alert warning using probability gain.

14.2.4 Use Case 4: Improved personal safety of employees and other members of the public

Current status: Manual alerts possible by the end of the project. Linking alerts to automated legacy systems is not part of the TURNkey project. If needed, this would be addressed in a follow-on project.

Next steps: Resolve how multiple thresholds could be accommodated for different CI's, and how these thresholds would be changed or updated (GUI needed for bespoke data entry). Clarify whether the alert would be audible.

14.2.5 Use Case 5: Reduced damage to critical systems allowing faster recovery after an earthquake

Current status: Manual alerts possible by the end of the project. Linking alerts to automated legacy systems is not part of the TURNkey project. If needed, this would be addressed in a follow-on project.

Next steps: Resolve how multiple thresholds could be accommodated for different critical systems, and how these thresholds would be changed or updated (GUI needed for bespoke data entry). Clarify whether alert would be audible

14.2.6 Use Case 6: Monitor the progress of response and recovery activities, including employee safety

Current status: All possible by the end of the project. The mobile app would be more applicable to wide-area CI than localised CI (e.g., single site)

Next steps: Test the use case with a real example during the development of the disaster management and resilience business model

14.2.7 Use Case 7: Initiate rapid activation of disaster management plans during and after an earthquake

Current status: All possible by the end of the project.

Next steps: Test the use case with a real example during the development of the disaster management and resilience business model

15 References

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16 Appendix A – Virtual Demonstrator Story Board

The virtual demonstrator was divided into 5 scenes.

Scene 1: Improving Resilience to Earthquakes across Europe

Narrative	Key images
<p>Welcome to TURNkey, a three-year research project to support improved earthquake resilience across Europe.</p>	
<p>Among natural hazards, earthquakes result in the highest number fatalities and cause the second highest economic losses.</p>	
<p>From 2006 to 2015, Europe experienced 21 earthquake-related disasters that resulted in 1,049 fatalities, more than 18 billion Euros in economic losses, and affected 284,000 people.</p>	
<p>This short demonstration video explains the background to the TURNkey platform and explores how it can help Europe become more resilient to an earthquake event.</p>	
<p>The presentation is divided into 4 sections. An overview of the TURNkey platform. An introduction to operational earthquake forecasting. An introduction to earthquake early warning and an overview of rapid recovery following an earthquake event</p>	

<p>At the end of each section a researcher will ask for your immediate thoughts on what you have seen and heard and they will answer any questions that you may have.</p>	
<p>The researcher will then play the video again, this time stopping at specific points in the video to get more detailed feedback on your understanding of the information presented; the usefulness of the information to you or your organisation; how you might use the information in your day to day activities; including communication with the general public, employees and customers.</p>	<div data-bbox="1058 759 1439 987"> <p>How easy was it for you to understand the information presented by TURNkey?</p> </div> <div data-bbox="1058 987 1439 1216"> <p>How useful do think the information presented in this section will be to you or your organisation?</p> </div> <div data-bbox="1058 1216 1439 1444"> <p>How might you use the information in your day-to-day activities, including communication with the general public, employees and customers?</p> </div>
<p>Finally, the researcher will ask if you have any suggestions for improving the TURNkey system.</p>	<p>Do you have any suggestions that could improve the way TURNkey presents the information to you?</p>
<p>Please be assured, any answers you provide will be treated in the strictest confidence and will only be used for the purpose of this research. All data collected will be stored and handled in accordance with GDPR rules.</p>	<p>Any answers you give will be treated in confidence and will only be used for the research project</p>

	<p>All data collected will be handled in accordance with GDPR rules</p>
<p>The TURNkey project has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. We thank the EU for their support.</p>	<p>The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821046</p>
<p>Please indicate to the researcher that you understand the intention of the research and that you are happy to continue with the interview.</p>	<p>Please indicate to the researcher that you understand the intention of the research and that you are happy to continue with the interview.</p>

Scene 2: TURNkey Concept Model

Narrative	Key images
<p>TURNkey is a scientific engine and graphical user interface supporting a cloud-based earthquake forecasting, early warning and response platform.</p>	<p>The TURNkey concept model</p>
<p>TURNkey is developing a new multi-sensor unit that along with existing seismic networks will continuously monitor ground motion at the national, regional and building scale.</p>	<p>A new multi-sensor unit</p> <p>ent/enhance (substitute) existing networks, build up new sensor n</p> <p>il networks SN 2. Strong-motion networks SN 3. Struc</p>

<p>TURNkey will integrate the sensor data with motion data captured on smartphones and eyewitness observations into a cloud-based forecasting, early warning and consequence prediction and response platform.</p>	
<p>The TURNkey platform will generate operational earthquake forecasts and provide continuous structural health monitoring reports to allow organisations and individuals better prepare for an earthquake event.</p>	
<p>Once an earthquake has occurred the TURNkey platform will broadcast early warning alerts allowing preventative action to be initiated to reduce losses.</p>	
<p>After an earthquake has occurred the TURNkey platform will monitor the real-time impact of the earthquake, including the probabilities of after-shocks, to support technical stockholders implement their major disaster response strategies; and support non-technical stakeholders and the general public to begin their recovery process.</p>	

	<p>The diagram illustrates the TURNkey system architecture. It is divided into three main horizontal sections. The top section shows monitoring and health monitoring capabilities: 'monitoring seismicity & other geophysical markers (strain, hydro-geology, geochemistry)', 'health monitoring' (monitoring of ground motions, max. accelerations, drifts, eigenfrequencies), and 'event (magn., distribution of motions, damage / level of confidence)'. The middle section shows 'Technical Stakeholders' (Critical infrastructures operators, Technical governmental agencies, Disaster management authorities) and 'Non-technical stakeholders' (Civil Protection, First Responders (SAR), Municipalities, regional agencies, Volunteer organisations). The bottom section shows 'The Public' (Citizens, Building owners/operators, Social networks, media). Arrows indicate the flow of information and 'send real-time alerts' between these groups.</p>
<p>Thank you for your attention. Do you have any questions about the TURNkey platform? Do you have any suggestions for improving the way the TURNkey platform presents information? To help you answer these questions the researcher will now play the presentation again. Please ask them to stop at any point if you want to make a comment or a suggestion.</p>	<p>A screenshot of a video conference interface. It shows a laptop screen with a grid of video feeds for participants. A yellow speech bubble labeled 'Your feedback' is positioned near the laptop, and another labeled 'Any questions' is near the top right. The TURNkey logo is visible in the top left corner of the interface.</p>

Scene 3: Operational Earthquake Forecasting

Narrative	Key images
<p>Operational earthquake forecasting, like extreme weather forecasting, aims to provide reliable and timely hazard information that can be used by government agencies, business organisations, critical infrastructure providers and members of the public to help them prepare for a potential earthquake.</p>	<p>The key images section contains three distinct visual elements. The top image is the TURNkey logo with the text 'Operational Earthquake Forecasting' below it. The middle image is a timeline diagram showing 'Short-term OEF' (Operational Earthquake Forecasting) and 'Long-term OEF' leading to 'OEF of aftershocks' over 'time', with a seismic waveform below. The bottom image is a collage of four photographs: people in a meeting, people working at a desk, a damaged building, and a damaged power line.</p>

This said, an operational earthquake forecast is not an earthquake prediction, it is a probabilistic assessment of the likelihood of an earthquake of a given magnitude, occurring at a given location, within a given time period: from a few hours to a few days.

The TURNkey platform will issue a warning if there is a change in seismic activity and will direct the user to a simulation of the potential impact that the earthquake would have on human, physical and financial losses. If a suitable simulation does not exist the user can generate their own from the OEF data provided.

SIMULATION STATE	VIEW MAP	VIEW DETAIL
Complete		

Simulation Request Form:

Simulation date from: [input field] Simulation date to: [input field]

Code: [input field] Description: [input field]

SEARCH THE CODE TO SEARCH: [input field] REQUEST INFO: [input field]

ID	DESCRIPTION	DESCRIPTION	REQUEST INFO
100121	Carriage 01	Carriage	21/08/2020 - 10/17
100195	Carriage 02	Carriage	21/08/2020 - 10/17

The TURNkey platform will generate loss assessment reports based on the simulation and will issue a red, amber, or green warning for individual buildings or assets. The TURNkey platform will allow the user to send messages to key individuals and groups that might be affected should the earthquake happen.

ID	DESCRIPTION	DESCRIPTION	REQUEST INFO
100121	Carriage 01	Carriage	21/08/2020 - 10/17
100195	Carriage 02	Carriage	21/08/2020 - 10/17

TYPE	STATE	ENABLE RISK	OBSERVATION
HIGH PRIORITY BUILDINGS		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1
SCHOOL		<input type="checkbox"/>	0
HIGH PRIORITY BUILDINGS		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0

The type of data presented by the TURNkey platform could include wide-area hazard maps at preset levels of uncertainty; or local area hazard maps at varying levels of uncertainty.

Hazard maps could be combined into an animation; displayed as a sequence that shows the forecast as a change in probability or as a forecast distribution along a longitudinal section, such as a railway track.

In addition to hazard information, forecasts could also include qualitative information; for example damage states or impact levels, or be presented in the form of risk assessments as part of an operational earthquake forecast dashboard.

Thank you for your attention. Do you have any questions about operational earthquake forecasting? or do you have any suggestions for improving the way the TURNkey platform presents operational earthquake forecasts? To help you answer these questions the researcher will now play the presentation again. Please ask them to stop at any point if you want to make a comment or suggestion.

Scene 4 – Earthquake Early Warning

Narrative	Key images
<p>Earthquake early warning systems provide advance notice of ground shaking following an earthquake.</p>	
<p>Once an earthquake has occurred ground motion sensors are used to detect and locate the earthquake's epicentre and to estimate the earthquake's magnitude.</p>	
<p>Earthquake early warning systems use the difference in speed between s and p waves to predict the time it will take for ground shaking to arrive at a given location. If the predicted level of ground shaking exceeds a preset threshold; the earthquake early warning system issues an alert.</p>	

There are a number of earthquake early warning systems in use around the world including ShakeAlert in the USA, JMA in Japan, SAS in Mexico and the Continental Earthquake Early Warning system in China; providing up to tens of seconds of advance warning of ground shaking; allowing people and systems to take preparatory action to protect themselves and their property.

When an earthquake is detected, TURNkey will issue an alarm: providing information on the location of the earthquake epicentre, its depth and magnitude, and an estimate of the time until expected ground shaking arrives at your location.

EPICENTER	DEPTH	MAGNITUDE
38° 14' 49" - 21° 44' 4"	50 Km	2 ML

TURNkey will regularly update the earthquake information, including monitoring of aftershocks allowing the earthquakes progression to be recorded and providing the real-time data needed to generate shake maps to show the extent of ground shaking across the impacted area. TURNkey will also generate GIS maps that give an early identification of built assets that may be at risk of serious damage.

DATE	DISTANCE	MAGNITUDE
05/05/2020 - 09:55	70 Km	1.5 ML
05/05/2020 - 09:57	60 Km	2.2 ML
05/05/2020 - 10:00	50 Km	2 ML

Thank you for your attention. Do you have any questions about earthquake early warning systems? Do you have any suggestions for improving the way the TURNkey platform presents earthquake early warning information? To help you answer these questions the researcher will now play the presentation again. Please ask them to stop at any point if you want to make a comment or a suggestion.

Scene 5 Rapid Response

Narrative

Key images

A rapid response to an earthquake by emergency responders, government agencies, critical infrastructure providers and business organisations can help minimise human and financial losses and increase the speed of recovery.

The TURNkey system will help support the post-earthquake recovery process.

Following an earthquake, the TURNkey system will provide updated information on the earthquake sequence and coordination information to support the implementation of recovery plans and procedures.

DATE	TITLE	TEXT MESSAGE
20/10/2020	CONVOCATION CDC ...	Convocation for early event ...
18/10/2020	CONVOCATION CDC ...	Convocation for early event ...
15/10/2020	CONVOCATION CDC ...	Convocation for early event ...

DESCRIPTION	STATE	TYPE
323485 UNRELIABLE MOBILE COMMUNICATION	IN PROGRESS	AUTOMATIC
323482 CLOSED CHURCH ACCESS	IN PROGRESS	AUTOMATIC
323480 SURVEILLANCE CONVOCATION	IN PROGRESS	MANUAL

The TURNkey system will describe a set of actions to be implemented if the earthquake has exceeded preset performance thresholds. In addition to providing guidance on what actions are needed; the system will also record what actions were taken.

DESCRIPTION	STATE	TYPE
CHECK GSM SERVICE	IN PROGRESS	AUTOMATIC
EDIT INSTITUTIONAL PICTURE	TO DO	AUTOMATIC
COMMUNICATION ALERT EARTHQUAKE	DONE	AUTOMATIC
CHECK FOR ELECTRIC CURRENT	REJECTED	MANUAL

Rapid and effective communication with disaster management teams is essential for post-earthquake recovery. The TURNkey system can automatically send predefined or bespoke emails to individuals or groups.

Predefined or bespoke messages can also be sent to members of the public or your customer base using social media channels.

Whilst many responses and recovery actions can be pre-planned and automated; some actions require human intervention.

The TURNkey system will allow the user to review the situation in the affected area. The user can drill down through the data to identify the need for further actions; or to review the progress of actions for specific assets or buildings.

A further drill down level will allow the user to initiate further actions for individual assets. These actions will generally be bespoke for each asset, for example enabling alternate communication channels if primary channels are damaged; closing or diverting access routes to buildings; or accessing alternative information sources.

An overview of the latest recovery situation is shown on a dashboard where the user can get an estimate of damage or losses.

Aftershocks are one of the most dangerous aspects of post-earthquake recovery. The TURNkey system will provide aftershock earthquake warnings.

Individuals responding to an earthquake will receive aftershock information, in the form of advance warning of ground shaking and be asked to confirm that they are safe once ground shaking has stopped. If the system does not receive the I'M SAFE message it will alert the control centre, and further actions can be taken. The system will record

the last known position of the individual, their affiliation and the follow-up action.

MAGNITUDO
2 ML

SECURITY CHECK	DATE SECURITY CHECK
✓	---
✓	06/05/2020 - 10:00
✓	06/05/2020 - 10:00

PERSON	POSITION	ORGANIZATION	CONTACTS
Mario Rossi	38° 14' 49" - 21° 44' 4"	CIVIL PROTECTION	06 999 888
Luigi Bianchi	38° 14' 49" - 21° 44' 4"	FIRE DEPARTMENT	06 666 444
Andrea Verdi	38° 14' 49" - 21° 44' 4"	POLICE	06 333 000

Finally, whilst the TURNkey scientific engine will generate all the data needed by the system to coordinate the recovery process, the inherent levels of uncertainty associated with the science means that it is often necessary to supplement this data with real-time, on-site observations.

355121 05/05/2020 - 16:07 1054

Mario Rossi NORTH-QUARTER CLOSED

NEAR DAMAGE RATE	MODERATE DAMAGE	SEVERE DAMAGE	COMPLETE DAMAGE
20%	40%	40%	0%

PERSON	TITLE	COMMENT
Mario Rossi	Comment 1	The Church was badly damage...
Luigi Bianchi	Comment 2	Many people who were injured...

TURNkey is designed to receive real-time observations and feedback via the mobile app. Users of the app can provide first-hand information on the effect of the earthquake on the level and severity of damage and the functional performance of an asset or building. The app can also be used to upload photos of any damage.

TURNkey

Observations

New Observation

Status: []

FUNCTIONALITY: []

AMOUNT OF DAMAGE: []

SCOPE: []

AMOUNT OF DAMAGE: []

SCOPE: []

AMOUNT OF DAMAGE: []

SCOPE: []

All the real-time information is stored by the system until it is checked by the user and either rejected or incorporated into the scientific engine, at which point the system will generate an estimate of the recovery time for an asset or building. In this example, it is estimated that Hospital A will require 36 hours before it achieves a minimum operational performance level.

DATA	FIRST FORECAST
Estimated Amount of Debris	400
ESTIMATED TIME FOR RECOVERY	
Hospital A	36 h
Hospital B	24 h
Hospital C	2 d
Road	1 d

Thank you for your attention. Do you have any questions about rapid response systems? Do you have any suggestions for improving the way the TURNkey platform presents rapid response information? To help you answer these questions the researcher will now play the presentation again. Please ask them to stop at any point if you want to make a comment or suggestion.

17 Appendix B Interview Guides

The interviews carried out on the basis of the virtual demonstrator with potential end-users in the Netherlands, France and Iceland were conducted on the basis of these interview guides.

17.1 English Interview Guide

TURNKEY PROJECT

T2.5 - Evaluation of the TURNkey platform (version 2.0) against end user expectations and requirements

CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS AND GENERAL BUSINESS ORGANISATIONS - INTERVIEW GUIDE (60MINS)

WELCOME (5 mins)

- *Introduction interviewers, Anglia Ruskin University and <TURNkey partner>, if present*
- *Introduction research:*
 - This research is part of **TURNkey** - a three-year European project that is part of the Horizon 2020 programme. TURNkey aims to contribute to the mitigation of earthquake risks by assisting stakeholders in different risk mitigation actions before, during and after a damaging earthquake.
 - In this part of the research, we would like to see how the information delivered by the TURNkey platform could contribute to disaster management planning and business continuity and how this would impact customers, employees, the wider community and the resilience of your organisation. Your contribution, and that of other participants in this study, will be used to guide the development of TURNkey going forward.
- *Confidentiality standards:*
 - The priority of the research is to understand your views. Please feel free to express a frank opinion.
 - Anglia Ruskin University and <TURNkey partner> abide by the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as well as all standard data protection regulations.
 - The session will be video and audio recorded and transcribed.
 - You – or your organisation - will not be identified in any of the reports or papers published following this study. Rather, the findings will be presented as an overview of the sum total of opinions expressed.
- *Check that participant is happy to go ahead. Please ensure that you have participant consent, either in writing or on the recording*
- The session will last around an hour
- Any questions?

START RECORDING

A. PARTICIPANT INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT (10 MINS)

The purpose of these introductory questions is to get an understanding of the participant's organisation; the organisation's current disaster management and business continuity plans for natural hazards (especially earthquakes); and the participant's role and responsibilities in relation to disaster preparedness, response and recovery.

Q1. Could you briefly introduce the **organisation** you work for?

Specifically:

- *core products and services*
- *where the business operates (number of sites, geographical reach)*
- *type of customers, business customers and contractors*

Q2. In terms of disaster management and **business continuity planning**, what does your organisation do to manage the risk of natural hazards, especially earthquakes?

During:

- *preparedness,*
- *response and*
- *recovery*

Q3. Now thinking of **your role** within the organisation, what are your main responsibilities?

Q4. What would be **your responsibilities** if an earthquake were to occur locally?

Q5. How does your organisation **communicate** internally and with its external stakeholders about natural hazards, especially earthquakes? I am including communications about how to prepare for an earthquake and how to respond once an earthquake has taken place?

That is, types, content and channels for disaster management communications

B. REACTION TO THE TURNKEY PLATFORM – BASED ON SHORT VIDEOS (45 MINS)

Participants are shown five short videos about the TURNkey platform prototype. The purpose of this is to assess whether the features included in the prototype address the participants' current needs in the area of disaster management and business continuity planning. Participants are asked to react to these features, state how relevant they seem, whether they are useful and what their likely impact on operations would be. They are asked for the overall appeal of the TURNkey platform and how likely they would be to consider using the platform. They are asked what they see as the drivers for / benefits of using the platform – and what barriers would withhold them from doing so. Finally, participants are asked to give suggestions for improvement.

You will now be shown five short videos that explain what the TURNkey platform does. The video clips are between one and four minutes long. I would now like us to view each clip together and I shall be asking for reactions to each one as we go along.

SCENE 1 (5 MINS)

Our first video clip will give you a brief introduction to the TURNKey project and platform

Timestamp	Comments / Questions
01:02	<p>The point of TURNkey is to improve <i>resilience</i> to earthquake hazards across Europe. In the context of organisations, this means improving <i>business continuity</i>.</p>
	<p>Q6. When you are presented with current and future risk scenarios (for business continuity planning) what kind of information do you value most?</p> <p><i>For example,</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>hazard estimates (e.g., most probably & worst-case scenarios)</i> ○ <i>hazard maps</i> ○ <i>exposure & vulnerability of critical assets (at different hazard levels)</i> ○ <i>damage and loss estimates (at different hazard levels)</i> ○ <i>cascading impacts, links between assets, potential 'failure chains'</i> <p>Q7. When it comes to managing a disaster event (earthquake), what kind of information (hazard, risk, impact) do you value most in the moment?</p> <p><i>For example,</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>automated alerts short before impact</i> ○ <i>regularly updated information on aftershock probabilities</i> ○ <i>probable damage to assets</i> ○ <i>probable functionality of public infrastructure (e.g., useability of roads and bridges)</i>
END OF SCENE	<p>As shown in the video, TURNkey provides information tailored to the three phases of an earthquake event: before the event; seconds before impact; and immediately after the event.</p> <p>The consequent videos will explore what the platform offers in more detail.</p>
	<p>Q8. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p>

SCENE 2 (5 MINS)

This next clip will show you where TURNkey will be collecting seismic information from and how it works together to deliver information via the platform

Timestamp	Questions
00:40	<p>TURNkey is a platform that provides earthquake forecasting, earthquake early warning and rapid response to earthquakes. It is both a scientific engine and a graphical user interface. It is cloud-based - and gets its information from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Multi-sensor units</u> – sensors placed in the ground which detect ground shaking ○ <u>Motion data on smartphones</u> – citizens with dedicated apps on their smartphones. The latter will automatically relay ground shaking information to TURNkey ○ <u>Eye witness observations</u> – from citizens or key people in first response, infrastructure or business organisations
	<p>Q9. What do you think of this description of the TURNkey concept model? Is it clear?</p> <p>Q10. The platform is cloud-based. What do you think about that?</p>
END OF SCENE	<p>The video has now given you an overview of the TURNkey platform. In the next three videos we are going to look in more detail at the features TURNkey provides for Operational Earthquake Forecasting, Earthquake Early Warning and Rapid Response to Earthquakes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)</u> provides information that is useful before the seismic event. It helps the end-user run current and future risk scenarios. It provides seismic hazard and risk estimates for a given region (or asset) at a given time. ○ <u>Early Earthquake Warning (EEW)</u> provides information that is useful 10-20 seconds before ground shaking. It issues an automated alert, warning end-users that an earthquake will happen imminently. ○ <u>Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE)</u> provides information that is useful immediately after an earthquake. It facilitates the short-term response by providing information on aftershocks and likely damage to assets and infrastructure.
	<p>Q11. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p>

SCENE 3 (15 MINS)

The next video clip provides an overview of Operational Earthquake Forecasting.

Timestamp	Questions
00:37	<p><u>Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)</u> provides information that is useful before the seismic event. It helps the end-user run current and future risk scenarios. It provides seismic hazard and risk estimates for a given region (or asset) at a given time.</p> <p>OEF is not an earthquake prediction, it is a probabilistic assessment of the likelihood of an earthquake of a given magnitude, occurring at a given location, at a given time.</p> <p>Q12. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p> <p>Q13. If you received a probabilistic forecast of an earthquake (for example, that there is a 10% probability of a severe earthquake during the next couple of weeks) how would you use that information (in business continuity planning)?</p>
01:18	<p>The TURNkey platform will issue a warning if there is a change in seismic activity. TURNkey will then provide a simulation of the potential impact of that earthquake on human, physical and financial losses. Users can also run their own simulations using OEF data.</p> <p>Based on the simulation, TURNkey will generate loss assessment reports. It also issues a red, amber, or green warning for individual buildings or assets. The platform also facilitates the sending of messages to key individuals and groups that might be affected should the earthquake happen.</p> <p>Q14. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p> <p>Q15. Do these features sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p> <p><i>The features:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Receiving an alert when there is a change in seismic activity in your area.</i> ○ <i>Being able to generate simulations for your area, buildings and assets.</i> ○ <i>Being able to generate simulations that shows the impact on human, physical and financial losses.</i> ○ <i>Red, amber, green (RAG) warnings for individual assets.</i> ○ <i>Sending messages to key individuals and groups that may be affected directly from the TURNkey platform</i>

<p>01:45</p>	<p>As the video shows, TURNkey could present the hazard data in the format of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Area wide hazard maps at pre-set levels of uncertainty ○ Local area hazard maps at varying levels of uncertainty ○ An animation showing the forecast as a change in probability from 'best case' to 'worst case' scenario ○ A forecast distribution along a longitudinal section (like a rail way track). <p>Q16. How clear is the data presented in the different maps? What is less clear?</p> <p>Q17. Which of the different maps presented would you find most helpful?</p> <p>Q18. Is there another way that this information could be presented that would be easier to use?</p>
<p>01:45</p>	<p>Forecasts could also include qualitative information on damage states or impact levels. The platform has a dashboard that should display the data in the format of a risk assessment.</p> <p>Q19. Do these features sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p> <p>Q20. What features you expect to see on the dashboard?</p>
<p>END OF SCENE</p>	<p>Q21. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p> <p>Q22. How relevant and useful do these OEF features seem to you overall?</p> <p>Q23. How could these features be used in business continuity planning?</p> <p>Q24. What would be barriers to using these features?</p> <p>Q25. What would the benefit of these features be?</p> <p>Q26. How they be improved?</p>

SCENE 4 (10 MINS)

The next video clip provides an overview of Earthquake Early Warning

Timestamp	Questions
<p>00:38</p>	<p><u>Early Earthquake Warning (EEW)</u> provides information that is useful 10-20 seconds before ground shaking. It issues an automated alert, warning end-users that an earthquake will happen imminently.</p> <p>P waves are the first waves to hit seismic stations and travel at speeds between 1 and 14 km per second, while S waves travel significantly slower, between 1 and 8 km per second. The S waves are the second wave to reach a seismic station measuring a disturbance. The difference in arrival times helps geologists determine the location of the earthquake.</p>

	Q27. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?
01:02	<p>There are a number of earthquake early warning systems in use around the world providing up to tens of seconds of advance warning of ground shaking, which allows people and systems to take preparatory action to protect themselves and their property. They include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ShakeAlert in the USA ○ JMA in Japan ○ SAS in Mexico ○ Continental Earthquake Early Warning system in China;
	Q28. Are you familiar with any of these Early Earthquake Warning Systems? If so, what do you think of them?
01:41	<p>When an earthquake is detected, TURNkey will issue an alarm: providing information on the location of the earthquake epicentre, its depth and magnitude, and an estimate of the time until expected ground shaking arrives at your location.</p> <p>In the future, there may be an option to integrate the TURNkey EEW alert with in-house automated systems. This would make it possible to automatically trigger a site's alarm systems – or switch machinery to a 'fail-safe' mode.</p>
	<p>Q29. Do this feature sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p> <p>Q30. How would you use this feature in disaster management planning?</p> <p>Q31. How could it be improved?</p>
END OF SCENE	<p>After an earthquake has taken place, TURNkey will</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ regularly update the earthquake information on the TURNkey dashboard ○ monitor aftershocks ○ providing the real-time data needed to generate shake maps to show the extent of ground shaking across the impacted area ○ generate GIS maps that give an early identification of built assets that maybe at risk of serious damage
	<p>Q32. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p> <p>Q33. How relevant and useful do these features seem to you?</p> <p>Q34. How could these features be used in business continuity planning?</p> <p>Q35. What would be barriers to using these features?</p> <p>Q36. What would the benefit of these features be?</p> <p>Q37. How they be improved?</p>

SCENE 5 (10 MINS)

The next video clip provides an overview of Rapid Response to Earthquakes

Timestamp	Questions
<p>00:49</p>	<p><u>Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE)</u> provides information that is useful immediately after an earthquake. It facilitates the short-term response by providing information on aftershocks and likely damage to assets and infrastructure.</p> <p>The TURNkey system supports the post-earthquake recovery process. After an earthquake, TURNkey</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ provides updated information on seismic conditions ○ coordination information to support the implementation of recovery plans and procedures. ○ provide guidance on the response actions that are needed
	<p>Q38. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p> <p>Q39. Do these features sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p> <p><i>Features:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>regularly updated information on seismic conditions</i> ○ <i>facilitation of coordination during response</i> ○ <i>guidance on the response actions that are needed</i>
<p>01:13</p>	<p>The TURNkey system can automatically send</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ predefined or bespoke emails to individuals or groups ○ predefined or bespoke messages to members of the public or your customer base using social media channels.
	<p>Q40. Do these features sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p>

<p>02:07</p>	<p>Many responses and recovery actions can be pre-planned and automated in TURNkey.</p> <p>The TURNkey dashboard provides an overview of the situation in the affected area.</p> <p>Bespoke for each individual asset: users can drill down through the data to review the situation and initiate actions (such as enabling alternative communication channels, diverting access routes to buildings).</p>
	<p>Q41. Do these features sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p> <p><i>Features:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>pre-planned and automated actions</i> ○ <i>the ability to drill down through the data to review the situation and initiate actions for individual assets</i>
<p>02:41</p>	<p>TURNkey provides aftershock earthquake warnings.</p> <p>After an aftershock, individuals involved in the response will be asked via a mobile phone app to confirm that they are safe once ground shaking has stopped. If no "I'M SAFE" message is received, TURNkey alerts the control centre, informing them of the individual's last known position.</p>
	<p>Q42. Does this feature sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p>
<p>END OF SCENE</p>	<p>TURNkey is designed to receive real-time observations and feedback via a mobile app. Users can upload first-hand information on level and severity of damage and on the functional performance of an asset or building. They can also upload photos.</p> <p>All the real-time information is stored by the system until it is checked by the user and either rejected, or incorporated into the scientific engine, at which point the system will generate an estimate of the recovery time for an asset or building.</p>
	<p>Q43. Any questions? Initial thoughts? Comments?</p> <p>Q44. Do these features sound useful to you? Why (not)?</p>

C OVERALL REACTIONS AND COMMENTS (5 MINS)

Q45. Based on what we have shown you, what are in your view the three most useful features of TURNkey to your organisation? Why?

Q46. Are there any features that you would not use? Why not?

Q47. What does TURNkey offer that you do not already have in place?

Q48. Do you envisage any difficulties in adopting the use of this platform in your organisation?

Q49. If you had to meet the TURNkey development team, what suggestions would you give to ensure that the platform is designed to help you meet your organisation's objectives and enable you to prepare for and respond more effectively to a seismic event?

Q50. Any other comments?

THANK AND CLOSE

17.2 Dutch Interview Guide

TURNKEY PROJECT

T2.5 - Evaluatie van het TURNkey- platform (versie 2.0) tegen de verwachtingen en vereisten van de eindgebruiker

INTERVIEW GUIDE (60 MINS)

Wat is TURNkey?

- TURNKey is een onderzoeksproject dat het doel heeft een data platform te ontwerpen om de aardbevingsveerkracht in stedelijke gebieden in Europa te verbeteren.
- Het data platform biedt een alarm tientallen seconden voor een aardbeving (Earthquake Early Warning); daarnaast biedt het probabilistische aardbevingsvoorspelling (Operational Earthquake Forecasts) en informatie ter ondersteuning van snelle actie na een aardbeving (Rapid Response to Earthquakes).
- Het doel van het platform is de besluitvorming rondom risicomanagement en response bij aardbevingen te ondersteunen.
- Het project wordt uitgevoerd in 10 Europese landen door een consortium van 21 partners. Groningen is een van de regio's waar het project zich op richt.

Wat is het doel van deze meeting?

- Mijn universiteit (Anglia Ruskin, UK) draagt bij aan het TURNKey project door use cases te ontwikkelen voor de ontwerpers van het platform.
- Wij doen dit door in gesprek te gaan met organisaties die in theorie eindgebruikers van het uiteindelijke data platform zouden kunnen zijn.
- Aan de hand van vijf korte video's over het TURNkey platform zou ik graag met je bespreken welke functies in het concept model waardevol zouden zijn voor de veiligheidsregio, welke niet – en hoe het platform volgens jullie verbeterd zou kunnen worden.

Reactie op het TURNkey platform – op basis van korte video's

Je krijgt nu vijf korte video's te zien die uitleggen wat het TURNkey-platform doet. De videoclips zijn tussen de één en vier minuten lang. Ik zal de video's af en toe stop zetten om om reacties op de fragmenten te vragen.

SCÈNE 1 (5 MINUTEN)

In onze eerste videoclip krijgt u een korte introductie op het TURNKey project en platform

Tijdstempel	Opmerkingen/ vragen
EINDE VAN DE SCÈNE	<p>Het doel van TURNkey is om de <i>weerbaarheid</i> tegen aardbevingsgevaaren in heel Europa te verbeteren.</p> <p>Zoals is te zien in de video, biedt TURNkey informatie die is afgestemd op de drie fasen van een aardbeving: ruime tijd vóór de aardbeving; seconden voor impact; en direct na het is gebeurd.</p> <p>De volgende video's zullen in meer detail uitleggen wat het platform te bieden heeft.</p>
	Nog vragen? Eerste indruk? Opmerkingen?

SCÈNE 2 (5 MINUTEN)

De volgende clip laat een overzicht zien van het TURNKey platform: waar TURNKey de seismische informatie vandaan haalt; en de samenhang tussen de verschillende componenten van het platform.

Tijdstempel	Vragen

<p>00:40</p>	<p>TURNkey is een platform dat Earthquake Early Warning (EEW), Earthquake Operational Forecasting (OEF), en informatie ter ondersteuning van Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE) biedt. Het is zowel een wetenschappelijke motor als een grafische gebruikersinterface.</p> <p>Het is gebaseerd in de Cloud - en haalt zijn informatie uit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sensoren die in de grond zijn geplaatst en die grondtrillingen detecteren ○ <u>Bewegingsgegevens op smartphones</u> – van burgers met speciale apps op hun smartphones. De apps geven automatisch informatie door over het schudden van de grond aan TURNkey ○ <u>Observaties van ooggetuigen</u> - van burgers of hulpdiensten
<p>EINDE VAN DE SCÈNE</p>	<p>Wat vind je van deze beschrijving van het TURNkey-conceptmodel? Is het duidelijk?</p> <p>Het platform is gebaseerd in de Cloud. Wat vind je daarvan?</p> <p>De video heeft je nu een overzicht gegeven van het TURNkey-platform. In de volgende drie video's gaan we dieper in op de functies die TURNkey biedt voor operationele aardbevingsvoorspelling, vroegtijdige waarschuwing voor aardbevingen en snelle reactie op aardbevingen.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)</u> biedt informatie dat nuttig is vóór dat een aardbeving plaatsvindt. Het helpt de eindgebruiker bij het plannen voor risicoscenario's. Het biedt een inschatting voor het aardbevingsrisico in een bepaalde regio (of voor een bepaald gebouw object) voor een bepaalde tijd. ○ <u>Early Earthquake Warning (EEW)</u> geeft informatie die nuttig is 10-20 seconden voordat de grond gaat schudden. Het geeft een geautomatiseerde waarschuwing - en waarschuwt eindgebruikers dat er binnen 10-20 seconden een aardbeving zal plaatsvinden. ○ <u>Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE)</u> biedt informatie dat nuttig is direct na een aardbeving – bijvoorbeeld over de kans op naschokken en de kans dat bepaalde gebouwen en infrastructuur zijn beschadigd. <p>V11. Nog vragen? Eerste gedachten? Opmerkingen?</p>

SCÈNE 3 (1 5 MINUTEN)

De volgende videoclip geeft een overzicht van operationele aardbevingsvoorspellingen.

Tijdstempel	Vragen
<p>00: 37</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)</u> biedt informatie dat nuttig is vóór dat een aardbeving plaatsvindt. Het helpt de eindgebruiker bij het plannen voor risicoscenario's. Het biedt een inschatting voor het aardbevingsrisico in een bepaalde regio (of voor een bepaald gebouw object) voor een bepaalde tijd. ○ OEF is geen deterministische voorspelling, maar het is een probabilistische inschatting van de kans dat een aardbeving van een bepaalde grootte op een bepaalde locatie op een bepaald moment zal plaatsvinden. <hr/> <p>Nog vragen? Eerste indruk? Opmerkingen?</p> <p>Stel dat je een probabilistische voorspelling voor een aardbeving zou krijgen (bijvoorbeeld dat er een kans van 10% is op een aardbeving met een magnitude van 3 in de komende weken), hoe zouden jullie die informatie dan gebruiken?</p>
<p>01:18</p>	<p>Het TURNkey-platform geeft een waarschuwing als er een verandering in seismische activiteit is. TURNkey zal dan een simulatie geven van de mogelijke impact van die aardbeving op menselijke, fysieke en financiële verliezen. Gebruikers kunnen ook hun eigen simulaties uitvoeren met behulp van OEF-gegevens.</p> <p>Op basis van de simulatie genereert TURNkey schadebeoordelingsrapporten. Het geeft ook een rode, oranje of groene waarschuwing af voor individuele gebouwen of infrastructuurnetwerken.</p> <p>Het platform ondersteunt het automatisch verzenden van berichten naar belangrijke personen en groepen die mogelijk worden getroffen als de aardbeving zich voordoet.</p> <hr/> <p>Nog vragen? Eerste indruk? Opmerkingen?</p> <p>Klinken deze functies nuttig voor u? (Waarom niet)?</p> <p><i>De functies:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Een waarschuwing ontvangen wanneer er een verandering is in seismische activiteit in uw omgeving.</i> ○ <i>Simulaties kunnen genereren voor uw gebied, gebouwen en infrastructuur.</i> ○ <i>Simulaties kunnen genereren die de impact op menselijke, fysieke en financiële verliezen laten zien.</i> ○ <i>Rode, oranje, groene (RAG) waarschuwingen voor individuele objecten.</i> ○ <i>Automatisch berichten verzenden naar belangrijke personen en groepen rechtstreeks vanaf het TURNkey-platform</i>

<p>01: 45</p>	<p>Zoals de video laat zien, kan TURNkey de informatie op verschillende manieren weergeven.</p> <p>In deze voorbeelden zie je de voorspelling – en de statistische onzekerheid van die voorspelling. Je hebt de optie om op de kaart de meest waarschijnlijke voorspelling te zien – maar ook het meest ernstige scenario of het minst ernstige scenario.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Op de eerste kaart dat een breed gebied laat zien - is het onzekerheidsniveau van tevoren ingesteld - Op de meer lokale kaarten zie je verschillende onzekerheidsniveaus - Dan is er een animatie die van ‘best case’ naar ‘worst case’ scenario verloopt – met het meest waarschijnlijke scenario halverwege, - En dan heb je ook lengte doorsnede (zoals een spoorbaan) waar het onzekerheidsniveau is de lengte is weergegeven. <p>Hoe duidelijk zijn de gegevens die op de verschillende kaarten worden gepresenteerd? Wat is minder duidelijk?</p> <p>Welke van de verschillende kaarten zou u het nuttigst vinden?</p> <p>Is er een andere manier waarop deze informatie kan worden gepresenteerd die gemakkelijker te gebruiken is?</p>
<p>01:45</p>	<p>Prognoses kunnen ook kwalitatieve informatie bevatten over schade of impactniveaus. Het platform heeft een dashboard dat de gegevens weergeeft in de vorm van een risicoanalyse.</p> <p>Klinken deze functies nuttig voor u? (Waarom niet)? Welke functies verwacht u op het dashboard te zien?</p>
<p>EINDE VAN DE SCÈNE</p>	<p>Nog vragen? Eerste indruk? Opmerkingen?</p> <p>Hoe nuttig zijn deze OEF functies voor jullie?</p> <p>Hoe zouden jullie ze gebruiken in risicomangement?</p> <p>Hoe zouden ze kunnen worden verbeterd?</p>

SCÈNE 4 (10 MINUTEN)

De volgende videoclip geeft een overzicht van Early Earthquake Warning

Tijdstempel	Vragen
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<p>00:38</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Early Earthquake Warning (EEW)</u> geeft informatie die nuttig is 10-20 seconden voordat de grond gaat schudden. Het geeft een geautomatiseerde waarschuwing - en waarschuwt eindgebruikers dat er binnen 10-20 seconden een aardbeving zal plaatsvinden. <p>V27. Nog vragen? Eerste gedachten? Opmerkingen?</p>
<p>01:02</p>	<p>Er zijn wereldwijd een aantal Earthquake Early Warning waarschuwingssystemen in gebruik die tientallen seconden voor een aardbeving een waarschuwing geven waardoor mensen en systemen voorbereidende maatregelen kunnen nemen om zichzelf en hun eigendommen te beschermen. Zoals bijvoorbeeld:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ShakeAlert in de VS. ○ JMA in Japan ○ SAS in Mexico ○ Continentaal systeem voor vroegtijdige waarschuwing voor aardbevingen in China; <p>Bent u bekend met een van deze Early Earthquake Warning Systems ? Zo ja, wat vindt u van hen?</p>
<p>01:41</p>	<p>Wanneer een aardbeving wordt gedetecteerd, geeft TURNkey een alarm af: het geeft informatie over de locatie van het epicentrum van de aardbeving, de diepte en omvang ervan, en een schatting van de tijd totdat de verwachte grondschudding op uw locatie arriveert.</p> <p>In de toekomst kan er een optie zijn om de TURNkey EEW-waarschuwing te integreren met interne geautomatiseerde systemen. Dit zou het mogelijk maken om automatisch de alarmsystemen van een site te activeren - of om machines over te schakelen naar een 'fail-safe'-modus.</p> <p>Klinkt deze functie nuttig voor u? (Waarom niet)? Hoe zou je gebruiken in disaster management? Hoe kan het worden verbeterd?</p>
<p>EINDE VAN DE SCÈNE</p>	<p>Nadat er een aardbeving heeft plaatsgevonden, zal TURNkey</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ regelmatig de aardbevingsinformatie op het TURNkey-dashboard bijwerken ○ waarschuwen voor naschokken ○ real-time informatie geven dat nodig is om kaarten te genereren die de mate van het beven van de aarde in het getroffen gebied te laten zien

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GIS-kaarten generen die laten zien welke gebouwde objecten mogelijk ernstig beschadigd kunnen raken
	<p>Nog vragen? Eerste indruk? Opmerkingen?</p> <p>Hoe nuttig zijn deze EEW functies voor jullie?</p> <p>Hoe zouden jullie ze gebruiken in risicomangement?</p> <p>Hoe zouden ze kunnen worden verbeterd?</p>

SCÈNE 5 (10 MINUTEN)

De volgende videoclip geeft een overzicht van Rapid Response to Earthquakes

Tijdstempel	Vragen
00: 49	<p><u>Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE)</u> biedt informatie dat nuttig is direct na een aardbeving – bijvoorbeeld over de kans op naschokken en de kans dat bepaalde gebouwen en infrastructuur zijn beschadigd.</p> <p>Het TURNkey-systeem ondersteunt de respons na de aardbeving. Na een aardbeving, TURNkey</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ biedt bijgewerkte informatie over seismische omstandigheden ○ helpt met het coördineren van informatie tijdens de uitvoering van de response en het herstel ○ geeft informatie die de responsacties ondersteunen

	<p>V38. Nog vragen? Eerste indruk? Opmerkingen?</p> <p>V39. Klinken deze functies nuttig voor u? Waarom niet)?</p> <p><i>Kenmerken:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>regelmatig bijgewerkte informatie over seismische omstandigheden</i> ○ <i>faciliteren van coördinatie tijdens de respons</i> ○ <i>geeft informatie die de responsacties ondersteunen</i>
01:13	<p>Het TURNkey-systeem kan automatisch berichten verzenden</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Op maat gemaakte e-mails naar individuen of groepen ○ Op maat gemaakte berichten aan inwoners via sociale mediakanalen. <p>Klinken deze functies nuttig voor u? Waarom niet)?</p>
02:07	<p>Veel reacties en herstelacties kunnen vooraf worden gepland en geautomatiseerd in TURNkey.</p> <p>Het TURNkey-dashboard geeft een overzicht van de situatie in het getroffen gebied.</p> <p>Gebruikers kunnen in het dashboard inzoomen op elk afzonderlijk gebouwd object voor informatie - om de situatie te bekijken en acties te ondernemen (zoals alternatieve communicatiekanalen activeren, toegangsroutes naar gebouwen omleiden).</p> <p>Klinken deze functies nuttig voor u? (Waarom niet)?</p> <p><i>Functies :</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>het vooraf plannen en automatiseren van response of herstel acties</i> ○ <i>Gebruikers kunnen in het dashboard inzoomen op elk afzonderlijk gebouwd object voor informatie - om de situatie te bekijken en acties te ondernemen</i>
02:41	<p>TURNkey waarschuwt voor naschokken.</p> <p>Bij een naschok zullen personen die bij de respons betrokken zijn, via een app worden gevraagd om te bevestigen dat ze veilig zijn zodra de aardbeving is gestopt. Als er geen "IK BEN VEILIG" -bericht wordt ontvangen, waarschuwt TURNkey het controlecentrum en informeert hen over de laatst bekende positie van het individu.</p>

	Klinkt deze functie nuttig voor u? (Waarom niet)?
EINDE VAN DE SCÈNE	TURNkey is ontworpen om real-time observaties en feedback te ontvangen via een mobiele app. Gebruikers kunnen informatie uploaden over het niveau en de ernst van de schade en over de staat en het functioneren van een object, infrastructuur of gebouw. Ze kunnen ook foto's uploaden. Alle real-time informatie wordt door het systeem opgeslagen totdat het wordt gecontroleerd door de gebruiker en ofwel wordt afgewezen, ofwel wordt opgenomen in de data engine, waarna het systeem een inschatting zal maken van de hersteltijd voor een object, infrastructuur of gebouw.
	Nog vragen? Eerste indruk? Opmerkingen? Klinken deze functies nuttig voor u? (Waarom niet)?

C ALGEMENE REACTIES EN OPMERKINGEN (5 MINUTEN)

Op basis van wat we u hebben laten zien, wat zijn volgens u de drie meest bruikbare functies van TURNKey voor uw organisatie? Waarom?

Zijn er functies die u niet zou gebruiken? Waarom niet?

Wat biedt TURNkey dat u nog niet heeft?

Ziet u moeilijkheden bij het adopteren van het gebruik van dit platform in uw organisatie?

Wat voor een advies hebben jullie voor het TURNkey development team?

Andere opmerkingen?

BEDANKT EN SLUITEN

18 Appendix C – Survey SWOT Analysis

SWOT Survey TURNkey

Dear colleague,

At the annual meeting in June 2021, a workshop was conducted to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) that mark the TURNkey project. Due to time restrictions, it was not possible to fully complete the analysis during that meeting.

The purpose of this survey is to obtain additional feedback on the SWOT analysis from TURNkey researchers. This survey consists of four sections - Strengths, Opportunities, Weaknesses and Threats. For each section, you will be asked to rate items on a Likert scale and (optionally) answer two open questions. It will take about 12 minutes to complete the entire survey.

The results will be published in D2.8. All who complete the survey will be listed as contributors to that deliverable.

If you have any comments or questions about this survey or D2.8, please contact Femke Mulder at femke.mulder@aru.ac.uk

Thanks in advance for your help and time.

Section 1

1. Please enter your name and organization *

Strengths

Strengths are internal to the TURNkey project (e.g., its features and support tools).

2. The following strengths have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the features below.

	This is definitely not a strength	This is not a strength	Neutral	This is a strength	This is a key strength
TURNkey provides an integrated system for all stages of the earthquake disaster cycle	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey provides an information cockpit / dashboard	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey provides regularly updated short-term earthquake forecasts (OEF)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Control of uncertainties is based on end-user preferences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Earthquake early warning (EEW) is based on customized thresholds	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey facilitates two-way communication during the RRE phase	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey provides forecasts for cascading hazard events (OEF)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey provides alerts for cascading hazard events (EEW)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

TURNkey provides real-time infrastructure performance status alerts (RRE)

3. (Optional) Are there in your view other important strengths not listed here?

Enter your answer

4. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could exploit its key strengths.

Enter your answer

Opportunities

Opportunities are external to the TURNkey project (e.g., demand and existing end-user processes and systems).

5. The following opportunities have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the items below.

	This is definitely not an opportunity	This is not an opportunity	Neutral	This is an opportunity	This is a key opportunity
TURNkey could improve public safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could improve occupational safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could improve public mental preparedness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could improve occupational mental preparedness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could contribute to better informed disaster resilience plans	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could enable the early activation of disaster response plans	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could make the danger first responders face better visible	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could make decision makers more aware of potential losses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey could support onsite facility control (e.g., for critical infrastructure providers)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

TURNkey could reduce downtime of critical infrastructures	<input type="radio"/>				
TURNkey could reduce business disruption	<input type="radio"/>				
TURNkey could improve contingency planning	<input type="radio"/>				
TURNkey could inform public information and education campaigns	<input type="radio"/>				
TURNkey could inform training programs	<input type="radio"/>				
TURNkey could raise awareness of earthquake management	<input type="radio"/>				

6. (Optional) Are there in your view other important opportunities not listed here?

Enter your answer

7. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could exploit its key opportunities.

Enter your answer

Weaknesses

Weaknesses are internal to the TURNkey project (e.g., its features and support tools - or lack thereof).

8. The following weaknesses have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the items below.

	This is definitely not a weakness	This is not a weakness	Neutral	This is a weakness	This is a key weakness
TURNkey has not been validated against a wide range of operational circumstances	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey has not been validated against a wide range of critical failure modes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is no guidance on how to integrate TURNkey with inhouse technical systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is no guidance on how to tailor TURNkey to different organizational needs or national disaster management systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is no plan for long-term system maintenance or upgrades	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No training or user-guidance is provided	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is no business model for TURNkey	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey uses unclear (technical/ambiguous) terminology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

TURNkey's cost (e.g., of sensor network maintenance)	<input type="radio"/>				
TURNkey fails to accurately model local seismic conditions	<input type="radio"/>				
The uncertainty of TURNkey OEF information	<input type="radio"/>				
The short-term notice of EEW alerts	<input type="radio"/>				
The absence of features desired by end-users (e.g., offline mode (RRE), 'all clear' notification (EEW), filtering capabilities for impact data, comparisons, access through smartphones)	<input type="radio"/>				

9. (Optional) Are there in your view other important weaknesses not listed here?

10. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could address its key weaknesses.

Threats

Threats are external to the TURNkey project (e.g., lack of demand and incompatible existing end-user processes and systems).

11. The following threats have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the items below.

	This is definitely not a threat	This is not a threat	Neutral	This is a threat	This is a key threat
A failure to integrate TURNkey with existing national disaster management systems and processes (resulting in gaps and/or duplications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A failure to integrate TURNkey with existing organizational disaster management systems and processes (resulting in gaps and/or duplications)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey's data is incompatible with existing end-user data formats (e.g., the use of color)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TURNkey is not accepted by existing disaster management authorities, local legal agencies or statutory bodies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is a lack of political support for TURNkey	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Senior level end-users lack understanding and/or confidence in OEF	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Unfair access and governance systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A failure to reflect local end-users' attitudes to risk	<input type="radio"/>				
Liability for false positives and false negatives (e.g., unnecessary business disruption)	<input type="radio"/>				
Failure to address IT security and data protection issues	<input type="radio"/>				
Users lack knowledge and resources to update platform	<input type="radio"/>				

12. (Optional) Are there in your view other important threats not listed here?

Enter your answer

13. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could mitigate against its key threats.

Enter your answer

19 Appendix D – Responses SWOT Analysis

The first question asked respondents for their name and organisation.

- The following strengths have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the features below.

[More Details](#)

■ This is definitely not a strength
 ■ This is not a strength
 ■ Neutral
 ■ This is a strength
 ■ This is a key strength

3. (Optional) Are there in your view other important strengths not listed here?

6 Responses

Responses

Turnkey integrates output of scientific algorithm into a platform for running operations. This is a pretty new concept.
provision of alerts beyond the territory of responsibility
1. Scientific engine is made flexible enough to handle various input format (default and user-defined hazard map, soil profile map, etc.).
Is a multinational project and unites researchers from research institutes, universities and private companies.
TURNkey provides long-term monitoring of buildings/infrastructures in the phases before and after earthquake events
The fact that uncertainties are shown is a strength

4. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could exploit its key strengths.

3 Responses

Responses

1. New data in various format (e.g., detailed regional hazard data, exposure data, vs30 map in tiff or shapefile format) can be input for a refined study, which helps improve the local earthquake disaster management in both retrospective and prospective scenarios.
Disseminate these elements on different channels (TV, internet, social networks, etc) to be known and used by interested people.
No concrete ideas

5. The following opportunities have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the items below.

[More Details](#)

- This is definitely not an opportunity ■ This is not an opportunity ■ Neutral ■ This is an opportunity
- This is a key opportunity

6. (Optional) Are there in your view other important opportunities not listed here?

3 Responses

Responses

Scientific engine could be easily extended to include the state-of-the-art mythologies from a long-term perspective.

TURNKey by itself is an opportunity for people working for its accomplishment.

Better streamlined communication between all parties involved before, during and after an earthquake

7. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could exploit its key opportunities.

2 Responses

Responses

2. During the development of TURNkey platform and during the long-term operation of the platform, new methodologies could be integrated into the engine, which would provide more reliable results throughout the disaster cycle.

Disseminate them to reach more people to take advantage of these opportunities.

8. The following weaknesses have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the items below.

[More Details](#)

■ This is definitely not a weakness
 ■ This is not a weakness
 ■ Neutral
 ■ This is a weakness
 ■ This is a key weakness

9. (Optional) Are there in your view other important weaknesses not listed here?

2 Responses

Responses

The computation cost (e.g., time and cpu) may be high, particularly for a large region with a huge number of buildings, infrastructure.

The platform has a lot of tabs and options. Users might get lost in navigating on the platform and get discouraged.

10. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could address its key weaknesses.

2 Responses

Responses

Cloud computing, parallel computing may be needed for large-scale estimation. However, extra cost for maintenance would be needed.

Through cooperation and discussions among members of the team could be found concrete ideas for addressing these weaknesses.

11. The following threats have been identified for TURNkey. To what extent do you agree? Please rate the items below.

[More Details](#)

■ This is definitely not a threat
 ■ This is not a threat
 ■ Neutral
 ■ This is a threat
 ■ This is a key threat

12. (Optional) Are there in your view other important threats not listed here?

0

Responses

13. (Optional) Please outline concrete ideas as to how TURNkey could mitigate against its key threats.

1 Responses

Responses

Making its actions understandable by all members of the team and by the people outside the project involved in cooperation work.

20 Appendix E - Application Workshop Hospital Scenario

Hospital Scenario

Purpose: to explore how TURNkey supports hospital disaster management during EEW, OEF and RRE – and how the platform communicates the hospital's damage profile and its performance profile

About the Hospital

- Name of the hospital: Hospital X
- Location: near TURNkey sensor network, in a high earthquake zone
- Average bed occupancy rate (in normal situations): 90%
- Total number of staff: 2250
 - N. clinical staff (e.g. physicians, nurses, healthcare technologists, etc.): 1500
 - N. nonclinical staff (e.g. administration, estates, engineers, etc.): 750
- Description: general hospital, routine services
- Population in catchment area: 350,000

Map
Hospital X

Map provided by Dr Federica Pascale—slightly amended for scenario by Femke Mulder

- Hospital functionality is shaped by
- structural + non structural damage
 - mitigation + response efforts

The San Fernando Veterans Administration Hospital suffered extensive damage during the 1971 Sylmar-San Francisco earthquake. At least 44 people were killed at the hospital. Source: USGS

Functionality Hospital Buildings

The building envelope includes the systems that separate the interior spaces from the exterior, both structural and non-structural. It includes exterior walls and cladding, roof systems, doors and windows, and floors or slabs that separate the building interior from the ground. Contents and equipment are completely dependent on the type of occupancy and the function of the space, and range from items such as furniture encountered in a lobby or a waiting room, to highly technical equipment commonly present in treatment rooms. In addition, laboratories, pharmacies, bulk storage areas, and large central energy plants have highly specialised and frequently very sensitive equipment. In general, both the building services systems and the contents of hospital rank among the most complex and expensive of any building type. Furthermore, **both the structural system and most of the non-structural systems are required to perform without interruption after an earthquake to enable adequate functionality**. In general, since the contents and equipment within hospitals varies substantially, damage types also vary widely. For example, medical equipment, such as operating tables and lights, radiation and X-ray units, sterilizers and patient monitors, is often heavy and not well anchored to the structure. Offices and storage rooms, such as the areas used to store critical supplies, medicine, medical records, chemicals, and fuel, can also be severely damaged by shaking.

Structural Safety Hospital X

- Good structural system design
- Condition of buildings no deterioration or cracks observed
- Condition construction materials no visible deformations; no rust
- There are no non-structural elements affecting the structure
- Separation between some buildings $i \leq 5$ meters
- Buildings have a high level of structural redundancy more than three lines of resistance in each orthogonal direction of the building
- Buildings' structural detailing, including connections are built according to a current standard
- Buildings' column strength is greater than the strength of their beams
- Foundations were designed according to standard and are not damaged
- There are no irregularities in building structure plan (rigidity, mass, resistance)
- There are no irregularities in the elevation of buildings
- Height of storeys differs by $> 20\%$
- High level of roof safety reinforced cast in place on concrete roof deck
- Good structural resilience to hazards (taking account of risk reduction measures in place)

No prior events affect structural safety

Non-structural damage to a hospital during an earthquake

Example of non-structural elements found in hospital facilities

Information for this slide was provided by Dr Federica Pascale

Examples of non-structural earthquake damage

Images adapted from FEMA 577 (FEMA, 2007)

Emergency and disaster management

- The hospital has a designated emergency and disaster management coordinator responsible for implementing the hospital's preparedness programme. This is their main task
- The hospital has an emergency/disaster committee. All departments are represented – and the committee fulfils its functions effectively
- All committee members are trained and are actively fulfilling their roles and responsibilities
- A programme for strengthening preparedness, response and recovery is being fully implemented under the leadership of the committee
- Hospital incident management procedures exist and are fully operational with properly trained personnel to assume different coordination roles and responsibilities
- The hospital has a designated EOC based in a safe, secure, and accessible location with immediate operational capacity
- Coordination mechanisms and cooperative arrangements with local emergency/disaster management agencies exist and are fully operational
- Coordination mechanisms and cooperative arrangements with wider healthcare networks exist and are fully operational

Emergency exits and evacuation

- The hospital exit and evacuation routes are clearly marked and free of obstacles to enable emergency evacuation.
- Emergency doors are not locked from the inside and do not impede an emergency evacuation.
- Automatic doors can be opened manually.
- There are audible systems (bells) that are used as alerts for evacuation
- Criteria and procedures are in place for the vertical, horizontal and partial evacuation of patients, visitors and staff to a safe location with the necessary medical, logistical and administrative support. The criteria enable triage for evacuation of patients.
- There are regular evacuation drills.

Disaster Management Responsibilities

- Disaster management coordinator Keith
- Responsible for operating theatres& clinical services: Federica
- Responsible for emergency services& hospital safetyNebil
- Responsible for wards& engineering: Mara
- Responsible for hospital administration Femke

People in hospital at time of earthquake

Buildings	Number of Staff: 550	Number of Patients: 1250
Operating theatres	50	5
Emergency services	30	30
Wards - General	400	1200
Wards – Critical Care	30	15
Hospital administration	40	0

21 Appendix F Hospital Use Cases

21.1 Operational Earthquake Forecasting: Employee and patient safety

3 months notice	2 weeks notice	72 hours notice
Review hospitals' emergency response plans in terms of effective plans for patient transfer, allocation of ambulances and operating rooms in hospitals and mobile (for high and medium severity injuries that require surgical procedures).	To decide whether to recall staff and stage mobile hospital tents and medical supplies for use as triage and treatment.	Fixing falling hazards
		Prevention of fire
		Emergency behaviour drill – training
		Activation of hospital command centres
Increase frequency of drills and emergency response and evacuation.	Review and test accessibility of cribs wheeled trolley, vest pockets and physical carriage methods.	Identify building to be evacuated
Increasing testing on the physical resistance of the physical environment may help boost staff's trust in the building.	Review accessibility and quantity of medical equipment needed for evacuation.	Maintaining power to alarms for leak detection
		Develop a more robust set of situationally-specific human responses
		Control the flow of flammable and ignitable liquids and gases

3 months notice	2 weeks notice	72 hours notice
To assess the risks in a specific environment through Hazard vulnerability analysis (HVA). The emergency management plan can be tailored to address the hazards most likely to affect hospital operations.		Postponing high-risk outpatient treatment and elective surgery until shaking hazards have adequately subsided.
		Decide whether to start transferring/evacuating patients (this requires a high level of certainty)
		Plan to degrade services: Normal levels of services cannot be maintained during disaster response. Identify services, such as elective surgery, that can be temporarily curtailed or minimized so that personnel and resources can be reassigned. (this requires a high level of certainty).

		Relocate staff and their families in safe areas close to the hospital
3 months notice	2 weeks notice	72 hours notice
The new staff training for emergency Uncertainty level: high		Employees and managers must review the action plan in case of an earthquake Uncertainty level needed: medium
		Remove obstacles from emergency exits and remove any object that can fall during an earthquake Uncertainty level: medium

21.2 Operational Earthquake Forecasting: Minimise business disruption

3 months notice	2 weeks notice	72 hours notice
Change the location of critical services to safer spaces within the hospital?	Relocation of non-care activities to a different site/ online	Refill Stock – both emergency stockpiles and ordinary working supplies
Non-structural retrofitting	Change hours of operation	Flow control of on-site utilities such as electricity, water, wastewater, natural gas, and liquid fuel
	Estimate business interruption costs and money needed to activate the risk management plan	Notify food services (to accelerate food delivery schedule)
	Emergency support financing can be estimated	The most vulnerable elements that can affect the functions of the hospital have been identified from past earthquakes, and are the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency generator • Bulk oxygen storage tank • Internal and external emergency communication systems • Patient elevators.

3 months notice	2 weeks notice	72 hours notice
	Re-evaluating the threat to oxygen, water, and power supplies, the loss of which would significantly reduce the ability of a hospital to provide care	Test accessibility of the hospital (external roads) and internal circulation routes.
	Back up supply of utilities	Back up computers/electronic records
	Business records and supplies are secured	Identify an alternate source for critical systems while nonoperative due to the earthquake (electrical system; telecommunication system; water supply system)
	Check validity/expiry dates of insurances	Check the efficiency of the uninterruptible power supply Uncertainty level needed: low
	Identify potential damage to critical non-structural components as architectural components or mechanical and electrical components. (Many of the hospital contents, such as furnishings and specialised equipment, which may be critical to hospital function, are not subject to building codes.)	Check the stocks of medicines in the internal pharmacy Uncertainty level needed: medium

3 months notice	2 weeks notice	72 hours notice
		Check the reservoirs of water are full Uncertainty level needed: medium
		Check that the emergency electric generator works and eventually repair it. Uncertainty level: medium

21.3 Operational Earthquake Forecasting: Joint planning (e.g., with civil protection)

3 months notice	2 weeks notice	72 hours notice

Develop intra & inter-state hospital networking and a full appreciation of ICU/NICU and operating theatres capabilities in the area		Guarantee access to education to the children of members of staff relocated in safe areas close to the hospital
Develop MOUs with private hospitals		Review the emergency plan in conjunction with the civil protection and other surrounding hospitals
Develop MOU with private ambulance agencies, critical care aeromedical transportation providers		

21.4 Earthquake Early Warning: safeguard personal safety employees

1-minute notice	30 seconds notice	10 seconds notice
	Exiting an elevator (the automatic system that opens doors at the nearest next floor)	Closing curtains to prevent injuries from broken glass
		Stopping high-risk activities (e.g. surgical operations)
		Securing dangerous items
		Exiting and stopping lifts
		Switching off the CAT, MRI or X-Ray machine

21.5 Earthquake Early Warning: safeguard personal safety patients

1-minute notice	30 seconds notice	10 seconds notice
Operations placed in a safe mode to prevent losses	Exiting an elevator (the automatic system that opens doors at the nearest next floor)	Closing curtains to prevent injuries from broken glass
Remove patient from CAT, MRI or X-Ray machine		Stopping high-risk activities (e.g. surgical operations) / Interrupting a surgery

		Securing dangerous items
		Exiting and stopping lifts
		Securing (vulnerable) patients
		Locking the stretcher wheels

21.6 Earthquake Early Warning: minimise damage to critical systems

1-minute notice	30 seconds notice	10 seconds notice
Elevators reaching level zero if empty	Secure gas cylinders	Turn natural gas off / Automatic shut off of pipeline distributing gas
	Ensure power backup generators are ready to work	Turn power generators on (if not automatic)
		Automatic switching of the supply refrigerating units that contain blood or other organic material or medicines from the main power line to the uninterruptible power supply
		Automatic switching of the supply of important computer units or ICU machines from the main power line to the uninterruptible power supply

21.7 Rapid Response to Earthquakes: enable a rapid and safe return to work

Assess damage
Restore critical systems
Remain vigilant for high risks
Check for damages to diagnostic machine (X-ray, etc)

21.8 Rapid Response to Earthquakes: minimise business disruption

Activate the emergency power generator if there is an interruption of the main power supply
Check the electric line if a blackout occurred
Check if elevators work

Check the structural damage eventually using the data of the real-time SHM system

Repair of water supply or electric line if damaged

22 Appendix G - Table of Features: What is Possible and in Scope?

The table below outlines the results of discussions at NORSAR 19-20 November. Some of the findings were challenged during the General Assembly.

EEW use cases CI and general business					
Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this?	Notes
EEW/ RRE	Minimise direct damage to critical systems & Limit injuries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey issues ground shaking alert directly to critical infrastructure provider / general business 	5	5 (indirectly)	Not possible in all locations This will be delivered indirectly via Civil Protection
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal alerts carried by individual workers, working in dangerous locations (e.g., at height, in confined spaces, at risk from falling objects) Systems that control vulnerable or dangerous assets (to automatically stop them or switch them to fail-safe mode) Tailored to specific organisations 	5	0 future - not during the project	Alternative: TURNkey app could also be used by employees
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey dashboard informs managers of automated actions by in-house systems triggered by TURNkey EEW alerts 	5	0 future - not during the project	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TURNkey issues the 'all clear' (i.e., no impending aftershocks) [based on OEF for aftershocks] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Workers can evacuate and report to their managers — Systems can be restarted 	0	0	Not possible. Instead, notification as part of OEF: regular updates regarding aftershocks with probabilities assigned
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical guidance on the integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with in-house systems 	5	Future – not during the project	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance on how to incorporate EEW in disaster management and business continuity plans 	5	Future – not during the project	
		0 = No, impossible 5 = Yes, definitely		

OEF use cases critical infrastructure and general business

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this?	Notes
OEF	Improve employee safety & Reduce disruption to business &	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TURNkey notifies critical infrastructure providers / general business of periodic changes in seismic hazard in the location of their assets (pull notifications). 	5	5	CI and general business access this feature indirectly via Civil Protection OEF before ground shaking is based on a hazard curve: it provides an estimate of the daily

Minimise cascading risks				<p>probability of exceedance of a given PGA value.</p> <p>This is customizable to the end-user (e.g., they can set the PGA value for the hazard curve)</p> <p>It does <i>*not*</i> provide a forecast of the timing and magnitude of an earthquake</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critical infrastructure providers / general businesses can use TURNkey to run simulations to assess the costs and benefits of actions at different shake levels 	5	Indirectly 5	<p>CI and general business access this feature indirectly via Civil Protection</p> <p>Before the main shock: for each shake level TURNkey has predefined actions and consequences for those actions. So users can run simulations.</p> <p>After the main shock: TURNkey only provides changes to the hazard level.</p> <p>After the main shock everything has changed (e.g., the building's seismic performance, the vulnerability, etc.). You need new models and TURNkey does not have that information.</p>

	TURNkey provides periodic changes in seismic hazard The organisation would consider the forecast against specific operational and business risk scenarios when deciding what action to take (if any) [same as 1 st feature]	5	5	CI and general business access this feature indirectly via Civil Protection OEF is not realistically useful for short-medium term business continuity planning: the changes to the probabilities that an earthquake event is coming are negligible.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey provides easy to read forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., “red forecast for the next 48 hours”) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managers can reschedule non-critical tasks Repair teams, backup systems, portable logistics equipment can be put on stand-by 	0	0	No RAG alerts, no associated timeframe No end time can be given. Instead: real-time updates during the aftershock phase. The technical feasibility of this feature has been lowered from 2 to 0 because the research done for this (by Strathclyde) includes assumptions that mean that it is not yet generalizable.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey provides critical infrastructure provider / general business and selected critical business partners with OEF alerts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint action to limit downtime and minimise cascading risks 	5	0 - Maybe in the future	
		N/A	5	

- Guidance on how to incorporate OEF in disaster management and business continuity plans

0 = No, impossible
5 = Yes, definitely

EEW and RRE use case civil protection and first responders – alert first responders

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this?	Notes
EEW /RRE	Headquarters can safeguard first responders' lives by alerting them to dangerous conditions on the ground.	A platform for two-way communication between headquarters and the field that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responders on the ground to assess the degree of danger before accessing collapsed structures 	0	0	Not part of TURNkey
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responders on the ground to take precautionary measures following their existing protocols if an aftershock is imminent 	5	5	Feasibility study in Mobile Testbed - TB8 The alert is provided through EEW, not through OEF
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responder decision-makers to communicate instructions aimed at safeguarding rescuers' lives 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responder decision-makers to monitor rescuers' wellbeing during operations 	5	5	The EEW app 'Safety Check' supports sending data about damage during RRE.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> incorporates early warning notifications 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EEW for aftershocks 			For EEW, there is no difference between the main shock and an aftershock. The same info is provided.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> has the feature 'rescuer status' (i.e., the "I'm safe" button) 	5	5	

		The platform should support the two-way sharing of information on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> impacted buildings 	5	5 (through the app)	Eye witnesses can select damage grades linked to functionality (TURNkey includes this) NB Only authorized users can upload eye witness info
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> other critical infrastructure (e.g., bridge) 	0 one-way only [engine to eye witness]	0 one way only [engine to eye witness]	Eye witnesses cannot input accessible / not accessible into the app. However, the engine can link damage states to accessibility/level of functionality. Damage states would be visually displayed on the map using a colour scheme.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> incoming aftershocks 	0 (not two-way)	0 (not two-way)	The two-way sharing of information on incoming aftershocks is technically challenging and will not be realized before the end of the project
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rescuer wellbeing 	5	5	Same as rescuer status, i.e., "I'm safe" button
					0 = No, impossible 5 = Yes, definitely

EEW and RRE use case civil protection and first responders – more effective data management

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this?	Notes
EEW /RRE	Decision-makers and communicators cut down on time and effort used to collate and process multiple and fragmentary data inputs.	A dashboard for first responders that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> has an 'earthquake cockpit situation report' feature 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rapidly populates with information from multiple sources (social media, network accessibility etc) 	5	4 – 5	TURNkey does not get data directly from social media -. this is done through the app.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> presents information that is comprehensive and continuously updated 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> presents information in a way that facilitates a rapid understanding of the current situation 	5	3-5	Requires trial and error with end-users
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> presents information in a way that enables decision-makers to prioritise interventions and allocate resources accordingly 	5	3– 5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> makes it possible to query information and drill down for detail on a specific area, element of infrastructure and critical building 	5	2	Operators of critical infrastructure provide the required input data via the app. Case dependent.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables users to relay information to decision-makers within their organisation and other institutional users. 	5	5	Features: user can provide information. Email options.

	End users responsible for alerting key actors cut down on time and resources required to do so.	An automated real-time alert registry/database for contact points at third party organisations and key personnel that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> is linked to TURNkey features such as 'automatic notification' or 'call to action'. 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> end-users can populate / modify beforehand 	5	5	
0 = No, impossible 5 = Yes, definitely					

EEW and RRE use case civil protection and first responders – improved coordination

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this?	Notes
EEW /RRE	First responders and external organisations involved in the response improve their coordination towards a more effective intervention.	An information/communication platform that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> allows all users to input information (rescue information) 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> allows all users to access information 	5	5	Depends on decision-maker
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> alerts external organisations 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> has a 'safe areas identification' feature 	5	5	Safe areas can be inputted into the system by users – this info will not be linked to the TURNkey engine. Status should be updated by eye-witnesses. Depends on input – before and during the crisis

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> has a 'damage assessment' feature 	5	5	Depends on input – before and during the crisis. This is done through the app.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> allows for eye witness information input (TURNkey and third-party apps) first responders have their own app. 	5	5 indirectly	Eye witnesses (civilians) should contact civil protection (or first responders) through existing communication channels. Before their info is inputted into TURNkey, it gets validated beforehand by decision-makers (e.g., civil protection). There is also the EMSC app which facilitates eye witness reporting.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> shows the evolution of the rescue operation 	5	4	Not the focus of TURNkey, but some TURNkey features support this. Responders can send notes to decision-makers via TURNkey. There is also a feature in TURNkey that allows responders to tick off tasks that have been done.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables external organisations to monitor the situation 	5	5	This is up to decision-makers. They conFIGure external users.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables the sending of instructions to external organisations 	5	5	This is up to decision-makers. They conFIGure external users.
	<p>The platform should include information on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> location and extent of damages, affected areas and infrastructure functionality 	5	5	Shakemap + proportion collapsed building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> emergency intervention sites and progress on the response efforts at those locations 	5	4	Same as 'show evolution of the rescue operation'

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ongoing prioritisation exercises of different emergency interventions during a response 	5	1-2	<p>TURNkey does not prioritize. Users need to do this by looking at the damage map, by running simulations. Not the focus of TURNkey. Simulations give an overview of what could happen.</p>
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24 Appendix H – Revised Use Cases

24.1 Use cases for Civil Protection (CP) and First Responder (FR) and Municipality (M) end-users

UC1: TURNkey to support understanding of impact to help plan a better targeted response

Goal	To understand the potential scale and sites of impact and enable the planning of a more accurate response
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clearly defined uncertainty parameters. Animated maps to highlight areas more likely to be strongly affected, with impact on key assets A manipulation of mapped info to allow comparison of zones before and after the forecasted earthquake The facility to customise scenarios along different criteria so that the end user can calibrate the response accordingly
Primary End User	CP
Secondary End User	FR
Success guarantee	Incoming OEFs allow the end user to understand the likely scale of impact in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> areas and key assets impacted relative severity and priority for intervention number of citizens displaced/wounded likely resources needed
Preconditions	Both end users have a fully updated TURNkey platform highlighting the following, clearly labelled assets, for their area: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High impact assets e.g. bridges and key road networks High vulnerability assets e.g. retirement homes, schools High danger assets e.g. nuclear or chemical plants
Success scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> OEF received TURNkey platform rapidly ‘populates’ with information on how the various asset types are likely to be impacted End user (CP): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plans safe routes for SAR and specialist teams Identifies safe areas for displaced citizens, tent cities and incoming first response organisations End user (FR): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gives advance warning to operating rooms and rescue teams ensuring that this are adequately staffed Checks conditions of infrastructure and likelihood of collapse

UC2: EEWs to enable a more rapid and accurate response

Goal:	To support a rapid and precise allocation of SAR teams to the most badly hit areas
Use Case Instance:	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shakemaps – to identify priority areas for intervention • Shakemaps highlighting priority areas for intervention according to the asset classification identified in UC1 • Shakemaps monitoring the health of strategic infrastructure e.g. hospitals and response co-ordination centres • EEW alerts that may be forwarded to chemical/nuclear plants and similar High Danger assets • EEW alerts to FRs in case of aftershocks • EEW alerts from wider geographical area, to give visibility of seismic activity in the region that may affect the end user's area
Primary End User	FR
Secondary End User	SAR teams on site (for receipt of aftershock EEWs via the TURNkey app)
Success guarantee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End users (FR) are able to get rescue units out of the station faster with clear intervention destinations • EEW aftershock alerts that enable FR to act to safeguard their safety and that of citizens in the area
Preconditions:	TURNkey sensors pick up seismic activity and signs of an imminent earthquake
Success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) EEW received 2) End user (FR) operations centre uses shakemaps to identify priority intervention zones 3) SAR teams sent out to accurately identified priority intervention zones 4) TURNkey information is integrated with field verifications from the SAR teams for a more comprehensive assessment of the overall situation 5) Aftershock alerts sent directly to FRs on site via the TURNkey app 6) Aftershock alerts forwarded to key selected parties e.g. townhalls, business, chemical plants etc. (if appropriate)

UC3: RRE to support prioritisation, resource allocation and co-ordination

Goal:	To increase SAR effectiveness
Use Case Instance:	<p>To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status of vulnerable buildings and critical areas, with evolution over time • Impacted areas by: number of victims, deaths and type of medical assistance needed • SAR protocols in place and players involved • Equipment being used • Intervention plans in place, with current status and key decisions taken • Visibility of all first response operations in the area • An 'I'm safe' button on the TURNkey app to be used by rescue teams on site • TURNkey remains active, providing updates beyond the first 72 hours
Primary End Users	CP and FR
Secondary End User	M (<i>limited usage</i>)
Success guarantee	End users receive continuous and comprehensive updates on areas of damage and compromised buildings, integrating SAR team verifications
Preconditions	In the immediate aftermath of an earthquake, TURNkey provides continuously updated information on the impact and rescue effort in the relevant areas
Success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) RRE information and ongoing evolution of the situation is centralised and visible on the TURNkey 'dashboard' 2) End user (CP, FR) identifies buildings and areas needing intervention and/or evacuation and mobilises intervention teams 3) End user identifies (CP) safe zones and buildings to move citizens and set up medical hubs 4) End user (CP) communicates with citizens on where to go if displaced or in a dangerous zone 5) End user (CP) uses information to co-ordinate the rescue effort across multiple organisations 6) End user (CP) uses TURNkey to send out messages to selected rescue organisations, key infrastructure etc. 7) End user (CP) uses information provided beyond the first 72 hours to assess recovery timelines 8) End user (M) uses TURNkey data in compiling damage reports

24.2 Use cases for Critical Infrastructure (CI) and Business Organisations (B)

UC1: Disaster and risk management planning at the individual site or building level before an earthquake event

Goal	To understand the potential scale and impact of different earthquake scenarios on built assets to better inform disaster management and business continuity planning
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> assessments of building damage states against the EMS damage grades for a range of earthquake intensity and location scenarios (with a minimum most like and most sever scenario) estimates of physical, human and economic losses based on typical building typologies or bespoke data provided by the end-user shake maps, PGA and structural damage states as input into 3rd party assessments of functional loss for key built assets.
Primary End User	CI, B
Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent ¹)
Success guarantee	OEF simulations allow the end user to understand the likely scale of impact in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> damage state assessments of their individual built assets which in turn will allow them to develop disaster and risk management mitigation plans shakemap, PGA and damage state assessments as input to inform an assessment of impact on functional performance (note: the TURNkey FWCR platform will not provide information on damage to non-structural elements, fixtures or fittings)
Preconditions	End users have full access (in terms of bespoke data input and outputs) to the TURNkey FWCR platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to enter bespoke details of their built assets or bespoke fragility curves (which will need to be generated by 3rd parties outside of the TURNkey FWCR platform) the 3rd party fragility curves are sufficiently detailed to allow reliable building level damage and loss assessments to be generated
Success scenario	Simulations provide a credible range of impact scenarios that allow the end-user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop effective disaster management and business continuity plans test their plans through training exercises and evaluate the practical application of their long-term service/business delivery location and supply chain partnerships (through application of TURNkey to assess the resilience of their key downstream and upstream partnerships) evaluate the necessity of disaster insurance for property/content damage and business disruption

¹ It is unlikely the critical infrastructure or business organisations will have direct access to the TURNkey FWCR system during the current development. As such access will be through the regional or national disaster management and response organisation. Direct access could be provided through further TURNkey development after the current project.

UC2: Disaster and risk management planning at the critical infrastructure sector level before an earthquake event

Goal	To understand the potential scale and impact of different earthquake scenarios on a critical infrastructure sector's (regional) built assets to better inform disaster management and business continuity planning
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> assessments of building damage states against the EMS damage grades for a range of earthquake intensity and location scenarios (with a minimum most like and most sever scenario) for all critical assets at the sector/regional level estimates of physical, human and economic losses based on typical building typologies generated from generic data provided by the end-user shake maps, PGA and structural damage states to allow strategic level assessments of functional loss for key built assets (strategic level functional assessments would have to be developed by 3rd party applications)
Primary End User	CI, B
Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent)
Success guarantee	Simulations allow the end user to understand the likely scale of impact in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> damage state assessments of their built assets across the sector which in turn will allow them to develop disaster and risk management mitigation plans, including redirecting service delivery to alternative locations that were less severely affected use the shakemap, PGA and damage state assessments as input to inform an assessment of impact on functional performance (note: the TURNkey FWCR platform will not provide information on damage to non-structural elements, fixtures or fittings)
Preconditions	End users have full access (in terms of data input and outputs) to the TURNkey FWCR platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to enter generic details of their built assets and loss ratios the critical infrastructure organisations critical built assets are located in a wider regional context that will allow an assessment of the functionality and performance of other factors (e.g., transportation networks) that could affect disaster management and mitigation plans
Success scenario	Simulations provide a credible range of impact scenarios that allow the end-user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop effective disaster management and business continuity plans <ul style="list-style-type: none"> test their plans through training exercises and evaluate the practical application of their long-term service/business delivery location and supply chain partnerships (through application of TURNkey to assess the resilience of their key downstream and upstream partnerships) evaluate the necessity of disaster insurance for property/content damage and business disruption

UC3: Business case for mitigation action to reduce the impact on critical service/business function

Goal	To understand the potential costs and benefits of mitigation actions to reduce the impact of different earthquake scenarios on the delivery of critical service/business function
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> assessments of building damage states against the EMS damage grades for a range of earthquake intensity and location scenarios and different built asset mitigation interventions estimates of physical, human and economic losses based on typical building typologies or bespoke data provided by the end-user shake maps, PGA and structural damage states to allow third-party assessments of functional loss for key built assets and services
Primary End User	CI, B
Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent)
Success guarantee	Simulations allow the end user to evaluate the cost/benefit of different built assets and facilities management mitigation actions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> change in damage profile and functional performance of individual buildings before and after physical mitigation (e.g., retrofit) interventions change in functional performance of individual buildings before and after operational mitigation (e.g., change in use or service delivery models) interventions evaluate costs and benefits for a range of mitigation actions and discuss scenarios/thresholds at which they would be implemented.
Preconditions	End users have full access (in terms of bespoke data input and outputs) to the TURNkey FWCR platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> provides a comprehensive library of fragility functions, and/or allows the end user to enter bespoke details of their built assets and loss ratios to recalculate reduced damage levels related to a range of mitigation actions the data provided by the TURNkey FWCR platform is sufficiently reliable to allow the losses of different mitigation scenarios to be evaluated (note: the costs of mitigation actions would be provided by 3rd parties)
Success scenario	OEF simulations provide reliable loss assessments that allow the end-user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> develop cost benefit analyses against a range of potential mitigation action suitable for inclusion in business (built asset and facilities management) models

UC4: Early activation of disaster management and business continuity plans

Goal	To trigger early activation of disaster management and business continuity plans during a period of heightened seismic activity before an earthquake event
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> daily assessments of the probability of ground shaking exceeding preset threshold levels
Primary End User	CI, B
Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent)
Success guarantee	OEF alerts allow the end user to:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • check health and safety procedures are fully operational • place key personnel on alert • adjust work patterns in anticipation of an earthquake event • protect critical systems • trigger logistic supply chains (e.g. deployment of portable generators and key recovery teams) • backup critical data • implement low cost and/or temporary mitigation actions identified during the scenario planning
Preconditions	<p>This use case will only be applicable to specific locations where local conditions are suitable for reliable probability gains to be identified at a level of certainty that would avoid too many false-positives</p> <p>End users have full access (in terms of bespoke data input and outputs) to the TURNkey FWCR platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to enter bespoke details of their built assets and loss ratios • the data provided by the TURNkey FWCR platform is sufficiently reliable to allow the losses of different mitigation scenarios to be evaluated (note: the costs of mitigation actions would be provided by 3rd parties)
Success scenario	Daily probability gain assessments allow the end-user to confidently trigger disaster management and business continuity plans

UC5: EEW to improve personal safety of employees and other members of the public

Goal	To improve the safety of people on site (or transport system) through the triggering of an early warning of ground shaking following an earthquake
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an alert warning of imminent ground shaking exceeding preset threshold is at individual locations would be sent to the organisations control room (this would most likely be a security centre, either located on site or at a remote third-party facility depending upon the organisations security arrangements)
Primary End User	CI, B
Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent)
Success guarantee	An EEW alert would allow the end user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • manually initiate an audible alert across the potentially affected buildings/transport system advising people to mentally (and if appropriate physically - e.g. stop or pause activities, ensure safety lines are secure, evacuate dangerous locations etc.) prepare for ground shaking and to drop, cover, hold • manually initiate a ‘go to safe mode’ instruction for hazardous processes and employee/public transportation systems
Preconditions	EEWs are received from the authorising agent without significant delay (too long a delay between the CP receiving the alert and it been passed down to the CI/B will negate this use case). End users have full access (in terms of bespoke data input and outputs) to the TURNkey FWCR platform to enter alert activation thresholds for their built assets and critical systems
Success scenario	EEW alerts received in a timely manner and building occupants understand what to do if an alarm sounds. Although it is technically possible to link the

	issuing of an EEW alert directly to automated control systems, this is not currently part of the TURNkey project
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UC6: EEW to reduced damage to critical systems allowing faster recovery after an earthquake

Goal	To reduced damage to systems that are highly vulnerable to shaking
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> an alert warning of imminent ground shaking exceeding preset threshold at individual locations would be sent to the organisations control room (this would most likely be a security centre, either located on site or at a remote third-party facility depending upon the organisations security arrangements)
Primary End User	CI, B
Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent)
Success guarantee	An EEW alert would allow the end user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> manually initiate 'shut-down or go to park mode' instructions to operators of critical equipment (note critical equipment would have to have been identified during the OEF simulation stage. TURNkey would not contain information about which equipment needs to be shut-down) open automatic doors (subject to security considerations) to allow egress from damaged buildings once ground shaking stops issue automated recall for key disaster response personnel to activate their personal disaster response protocols (e.g., to initiate the disaster response command and control committee, initiate their health and safety checks etc.)
Preconditions	EEWs are received from the authorising agent without significant delay (too long a delay between the CP receiving the alert and it been passed down to the CI/B will negate this use case). End users have full access (in terms of bespoke data input and outputs) to the TURNkey FWCR platform to enter alert activation thresholds for their built assets and critical systems
Success scenario	EEW alerts received in a timely manner and critical systems are set to 'safe-mode'. Although it is technically possible to link the issuing of an EEW alert directly to automated control systems, this is not currently part of the TURNkey project

UC7: EEW/RRE to initiate early activation of disaster management plans

Goal	To improve the safety of people on site through early activation of disaster management plans
Use Case Instance	To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> early assessments (within 30 minutes of ground shaking) of earthquake intensity and estimated damage states for critical built assets regular updates of shake maps, damage and loss estimates if TURNkey sensors are fitted within a building, bespoke estimates of acceleration and inter-storey drift at the building level automated email and messaging system (including social media) for key employees and other stakeholders
Primary End User	CI, B

Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent)
Success guarantee	<p>An early estimates of ground shaking and damage state would allow the end user to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dispatch security and inspection teams to provide a real-time observational assessment of the actual damage state and functional capacity of the buildings with the most predicted damage state • information received from real-time observation would allow disaster management plans to be modified to reflect the actual situation on the ground <p>The automated email and messaging system would allow the end-user to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • convene their disaster management committee and activate standard response protocols • inform key external stakeholders (including where appropriate members of the general public) of potential issues as part of stakeholder relationship management
Preconditions	<p>The end-user has direct access to the TURNkey FWCR platform through the authorising agent to allow operational decisions to be actioned and recorded in real-time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication systems, email and social media channels must be robust and operational after an earthquake
Success scenario	<p>EEW alerts and early RRE damage and loss assessments are received in a timely manner and initial real-time assessments of damage states and functional performance are gathered (see UC10 for further details) that can directly inform local earthquake response and recovery actions, including early advice to external stakeholders (e.g. customers, regional/national disaster response agencies etc.) on service level functionality and estimated time of recovery</p>

UC8: RRE to monitor the progress of response and recovery activities, including employee safety

Goal	To monitor the progress of recovery activities, including safety of those undertaking the activities
Use Case Instance	<p>To achieve this goal TURNkey will provide the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a mobile app to each authorised employee engaged in the response and recovery process that will allow real-time reporting of actual damage state (including photographs) and functional performance of individual buildings to the TURNkey FWCR platform • early warning of potential ground shaking and an 'I'm safe' function to monitor the status of employees • regular updates and progress reports (via the TURNkey dashboard) of predefined disaster response protocols developed during the simulations
Primary End User	CI, B
Secondary End User	CP (as authorising agent)
Success guarantee	<p>Real-time reporting and updating of damage state would allow the end user to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • modify standard disaster management and response protocols and dispatch appropriate teams to address the real needs on the ground • issue advance warning of potential ground shaking requiring teams on the ground to move away from confirmed (through real-time assessments against EMS damage grades) damaged buildings • monitor the progress of recovery operations on a single dashboard

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use of the 'I'm safe' function of the mobile app will allow central control room to monitor the safety of individual employees if ground shaking occurs
Preconditions	<p>The end-user has direct access to the TURNkey FWCR platform through the authorising agent to allow operational decisions to be actioned and recorded in real-time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication systems must be robust and operational after an earthquake; both between the end-user and their employees/external stakeholders and between the authorising agent and the TURNkey FWCR platform
Success scenario	<p>RRE dashboard provides a single source for command and control of the response and recovery process resulting in more efficient actions; better customer/external stakeholder relationship management; and a more rapid recovery leading to reduced long-term critical infrastructure/business losses</p>